

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

Deliverable n°:	D7.3
Deliverable name:	Business models and economic studies
Version:	3.0
Release date:	16.01.2025
Type:	Report (R)
Dissemination level:	Public (PU)
Status:	Final
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Co-funded by
the European Union

Change Records

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
V1.0	5/12/2024	Final draft	Luis Lopes, Emese Karácsonyi
V2.0	13/12/2024	Final version	Luis Lopes, Emese Karácsonyi
V3.0	14/01/2025	Final version with corrected tables 4 and 5	Luis Lopes, Emese Karácsonyi

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Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP / Task
All WPs and Tasks

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
CAC	Customer Acquisition Cost
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
CSAT	Customer Satisfaction Score
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HEBM	High Energy Ball Milling
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPV	Net Present Value
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
PV	Photo-Voltaic
R&D	Research and Development
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
ROI	Return On Investment
RT	Room Temperature
SAM	Serviceable Available Market
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SOM	Serviceable Obtainable Market
SPS	Spark Plasma Sintering
TAM	Total Addressable Market
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
TE	Thermoelectric(s)
TEG	Thermoelectric Generator
TH	Tetrahedrite
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UVP	Unique Value Proposition
ZT	Figure of Merit

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the findings of a comprehensive assessment of the macroeconomic and microeconomic dimensions of the START technology, a system for generating electricity from waste heat using tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric (TE) devices. The study focused on evaluating the industrial and economic viability of establishing a sustainable value chain for these TE systems, highlighting START's performance compared to conventional TE materials, technologies and commercial applications.

It provides a macroeconomic analysis, detailing projected impacts of the START technology at both the European Union (EU) and global levels. It outlines the value and supply chains associated with tetrahedrite-based TE systems, offering insights for stakeholders to gauge the economic potential within this ecosystem. The analysis presents an overarching vision for integrating START technology within the broader economy, emphasizing its role in building a resilient, mineral-abundant value chain.

Analysis of the microeconomic aspects, business and economic factors specific to close-to-market START applications was performed. Through case studies, potential for developing practical applications was modelled. Capital expenditure and operational costs relative to competing technologies were estimated. To facilitate rapid decision-making, models and tools were created for cost calculation, investment analysis, and business development, supporting the commercial pathway for new products within the START ecosystem.

The project outcomes underscore the strategic importance of START in reducing the EU's reliance on critical raw materials, promoting circular economy principles, and enhancing energy efficiency. By utilizing tetrahedrite-based TE systems, the START technology contributes to lowering fossil fuel dependence and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The report's insights on START's industrial feasibility and adaptability lay the groundwork for future expansion, positioning START as a scalable solution that can evolve with market demands and environmental goals.

1 INTRODUCTION

The present D7.3 report summarizes project findings and results on the exploration of macro- and microeconomic aspects of the START technology along the value chain. Work focused on the assessment of the industrial and economic viability of a value chain built on tetrahedrite-based TE systems and devices to generate electricity from waste heat. The START technology was reviewed along economic and feasibility factors and performance indicators, was compared with conventional TE materials, technologies and providers.

Macroeconomic aspects including projections on EU and global level are explored in Chapter 2 where an overall vision of the general START value and supply chains is provided. This macroeconomic analysis offers a wide view and is meant to help partners inside and outside of the ecosystem to better understand the potential along the value chain for tetrahedrite-based TE systems.

Besides painting the overall picture of the value chain, Chapter 3 is dedicated to microeconomic aspects where business and economic analysis of value and supply chains dedicated to practical applications were performed and modelled. The examples of close-to-market START applications were examined from all essential aspects of the present and future ecosystem of TE devices focusing on practical applicability, capital expenditures and operational costs compared to solutions available on the market. Models and tools have been developed and designed for cost-calculation and investment comparison to facilitate rapid concept modelling, support evaluation and business decision-making and business development of new products and services along the START value chain.

The above activities further enabled adjusting the overall picture and paths to be followed for reaching the impacts desired by the project including the reduction of EU's dependence on primary critical raw materials, the promotion of circular economy processes for creating value in the EU by building a strategic ecosystem based on a high-abundant minerals such as the START p-type tetrahedrite and the production of TE energy harvesting systems offering a contribution to the reduction of fossil fuels consumption via the increase of the overall energy efficiency and to the reduction of the greenhouse gas emissions.

Work towards obtaining clarity on the industrial viability and feasibility of the START value chain is essential for future exploitation of START technologies. Work presented in this deliverable can be replicated to update the current value chains considering the major macro and microeconomic factors that may change in the future, while models may be suitable for creating new value chains following the market demand and potential niches.

2 START ECONOMICS – GENERAL ASPECTS

2.1 MACROECONOMIC ASPECTS

An analysis on macroeconomic studies with projections on EU and global level is presented to grant a better understanding of the scope and potential of using TE devices and systems, especially those using tetrahedrite, as feasible energy generating options for different types of end-users.

Tetrahedrite-based TE devices present a promising solution to some of the key challenges faced by energy-intensive industries, particularly concerning reducing greenhouse gas emissions and improving sustainability. These devices have the potential to significantly lower carbon footprints by recovering waste heat and converting it into electricity. Additionally, they could help rejuvenate industrial sectors by creating jobs related to the exploration, processing, and production of TE devices and systems, thus contributing to broader economic growth (Freer & Powell, 2019).

The macroeconomic analysis conducted as part of the START project examines the economic viability of utilizing mining waste for energy generation through tetrahedrite-based TE devices. By repurposing tetrahedrite, a mineral frequently found in mining waste of copper mines, the project presents a sustainable approach to improving resource efficiency, energy recovery, and reducing environmental impact. The key macroeconomic factors influencing the adoption and success of these tetrahedrite-based TE technologies include the supply and demand dynamics of copper and antimony, government policies, the global transition toward clean energy, and the competitive landscape of the TE market.

2.1.1 Market dynamics

Macroeconomic volatility

Macroeconomic volatility in general refers to the fluctuations and unpredictability observed in key economic indicators, such as GDP, inflation, exchange rates, interest rates, unemployment, and money supply. It quantifies the uncertainty in these variables over time, often leading to adverse consequences for long-term economic growth (Aizenman & Pinto, 2005). In the case of START technologies, major volatility impacts derive from raw material prices, technology maturity and utilization, energy market dynamics and mineral extraction potential of tetrahedrites. These aspects are discussed in this chapter.

Impact of mineral extraction for Thermoelectric Generators (TEGs)

The mineral extraction and raw materials supply undertaken as part of the START project for TEG production is unlikely to negatively affect macroeconomic volatility. For the START TEG line, the necessary materials will be primarily sourced from mining waste and in relatively small volumes, which should not compromise the overall economic advantages of the technology. Other raw materials (i.e. for n-type thermoelements), despite not being obtained from waste, will be required in small quantities. Regardless, this is important to consider because, while mineral exploration and extraction should theoretically generate substantial income, drive economic growth, and improve societal welfare in resource-rich countries, historical evidence often indicates the opposite. Many countries with abundant mineral resources or experiencing mining booms have witnessed slower and more volatile long-term economic growth compared to countries with fewer mineral resources. The rapid expansion of the mining sector can hinder the development of other industries, a phenomenon known as the "Resource Curse" or "Dutch Disease." This phenomenon occurs when

a boom in natural resource exports leads to an appreciation of the national currency, diminishing the competitiveness of other export-oriented sectors (Brahmbhatt et al., 2010). Additionally, tetrahedrites are relatively common minerals with a widespread global distribution, so their extraction is unlikely to result in supply or price shocks that could destabilize the broader economy (Awe, 2010).

Dealing with the macroeconomic impact of TEG production and utilization

A strategic approach that balances short-term gains with long-term economic stability is key. Governments must prioritize economic diversification and invest resource revenues into other productive sectors, such as manufacturing and technology. In the context of TEG production using tetrahedrites as main constituents, the markets for copper and antimony, the key materials, are likely to experience the most significant impact. A strategic approach involving a well-regulated extraction industry coupled with the promotion of domestic TEG manufacturing could mitigate over-dependence on raw material imports and enhance the value added along the value and supply chains (Moutanabbir & Noureldin, 2020).

TEGs offer distinct advantages when it comes to integrating into the power grid compared to other renewable energy technologies like solar or wind. TEGs can harness waste heat from industrial processes, geothermal energy, or even the steady thermal output from power plants and vehicles. These heat sources are generally constant and not subject to the same environmental fluctuations that affect solar and wind power, such as changing weather patterns or daylight availability. Since TEGs rely on a steady flow of heat, the electricity they generate is much more predictable, making it easier for grid operators to balance supply and demand in real time. This consistency simplifies grid management, reducing the need for expensive energy storage solutions or demand-response strategies required to handle fluctuations in power generation.

Moreover, the modular nature of TEGs allows for their deployment in a range of settings, from local waste heat recovery to large-scale geothermal projects. This flexibility can enhance distributed generation without placing a strain on the existing grid infrastructure. TEGs can operate continuously and contribute to base-load power and can also be used as dispatchable energy sources. In contrast, renewables like solar and wind may require grid balancing mechanisms, such as demand-response strategies or backup generators. Additionally, new energy sources can alter grid frequency and voltage levels, requiring advanced control systems. For instance, solar and wind's rapid output changes may require fast-acting frequency regulation, while steady sources like TEGs can enhance voltage stability.

In summary, TEGs are easier to integrate into the power grid because their energy sources — whether industrial waste heat, geothermal, or other thermal processes — are stable and predictable. This reduces the need for complex management tools, costly energy storage, and reactive grid adjustments, making TEGs a valuable component of a balanced, sustainable energy mix (Venkatraman et al., 2020).

Modelling the impact of TEGs on the power grid

Accurately modeling the effects of new energy sources, such as TEGs, on power grid management is crucial for maintaining grid stability, reliability, and efficiency. With the integration of diverse energy sources, grid operators must account for different power generation characteristics — such as intermittency, predictability, and the ability to scale output — each of which can impact the overall performance and resilience of the grid.

To model the effects of new energy sources, several critical variables must be considered (Lannoye et al., 2011):

- **Generation patterns:** Each energy source has unique generation profiles. Solar and wind, for instance, are intermittent and weather-dependent, whereas TEGs, similar to geothermal, offer more consistent, predictable output. These patterns must be incorporated into models to simulate how they influence supply-demand balancing.
- **Load forecasting:** As new energy sources are added, grid models need to predict how electricity demand evolves. Renewable energy sources introduce complexities in matching supply to demand in real-time, requiring load forecasts that account for fluctuations in renewable generation and electricity consumption patterns.
- **Energy storage needs:** Grid models must include potential storage solutions like batteries, which are increasingly important for balancing the intermittent nature of renewables. By simulating energy storage capacities, response times, and costs, models can determine how storage interacts with new energy sources to enhance grid stability.
- **Grid flexibility:** The capacity of the power grid to adapt to rapidly changing supply conditions is another critical factor. Modelling grid flexibility involves analyzing the role of smart grids, demand-response technologies, and flexible backup power sources in absorbing fluctuations from intermittent sources or handling high base-load generation from sources like TEGs.

Several advanced tools and models, such as GTAP (Global Trade Analysis Project), PLEXOS Energy Modeling Software, and EnergyPLAN, are used to model the effects of integrating new energy sources into the grid. These tools allow for a detailed analysis of different energy generation technologies, grid management strategies, and future policy changes, helping decision-makers to plan grid operations effectively (Pina et al., 2013; Anderson et al., 2017).

Ultimately, the power grid models can be used for scenario analysis/forecasting to explore various future conditions, such as higher penetration of renewables, increased reliance on TEGs, or shifts in energy policy. These scenarios help grid operators understand potential challenges and benefits under different levels of integration and forecast the most likely outcomes. For example, one scenario could model the impact of a significant increase in wind and solar energy combined with TEGs as a steady base-load provider. Another might focus on the economic benefits of widespread TEG deployment in industrial sectors, feeding excess electricity back into the grid.

The modeling of new energy sources in power grid management is a critical process that helps predict and mitigate potential risks, optimize energy flow, and ensure grid stability. By integrating variables such as generation patterns, storage needs, and economic factors, these models provide a roadmap for transitioning to a more diversified, sustainable, and resilient energy grid.

Energy and commodity prices and their influence on macroeconomic volatility

The production of TEGs is vulnerable to fluctuations in energy and commodity prices, which can impact their overall economic viability and broader macroeconomic conditions. This fluctuation can have several macroeconomic impacts:

- **Inflationary pressures:** Higher input costs for TEG manufacturers, seen in higher raw materials and consumables prices, may increase consumer prices for TEGs, contributing to broader inflation, particularly if TEGs are widely used in energy-intensive sectors.

- Exchange rate changes: Countries importing raw materials for TEG production may face currency volatility as commodity prices rise. Higher import costs can weaken a country's currency, reducing competitiveness in other industries and increasing inflation. This aspect is lessened if materials are internally sourced, such as the case for the use of tetrahedrites from waste in European mines.
- Investment volatility: Uncertainty around energy and commodity prices can affect investment decisions in TEG technology. Investors, especially private ones, may be hesitant to fund TEG projects if raw material costs are unpredictable, compared to other renewable technologies with more stable value and supply chains.

The START project's TEG devices use tetrahedrite, a mineral extracted from mining waste, which is less prone to market price fluctuations. However, the main elements of this mineral, copper and antimony, are considered important commodities: the most recent EU Critical Raw Materials list (European Commission, 2023) has Antimony as a critical raw material, while Copper is listed as a strategic raw material (copper does not meet the CRM thresholds but is included on the CRM list as strategic raw material in line with the Critical Raw Materials Act), highlighting their importance for the European industry. Variations in the prices of these materials can indirectly influence the manufacturing costs of TEGs, consequently affecting their market competitiveness.

Copper, an element present in certain thermoelectric materials, including tetrahedrites, experiences price fluctuations driven by global demand, particularly from industries like construction and electronics, as well as supply-side factors such as mining disruptions or geopolitical events. In contrast, using copper in other energy generation technologies that can be deployed more broadly may be more cost-effective than manufacturing TEGs. Antimony, though used in smaller quantities, is more niche and subject to significant price volatility due to its limited supply and concentrated production in specific regions, such as China. Any disruption in their supply can lead to price spikes. Rising commodity prices may then potentially reduce the competitiveness of TEGs compared to other renewable energy technologies.

TEGs are typically deployed in settings where waste heat is available and can be converted into usable electricity. The key factor determining their viability is the cost of alternative energy sources. If energy prices, especially for electricity or fossil fuels, are high, the economic case for TEG utilization strengthens. TEGs offer a cost-saving measure by capturing energy that would otherwise be lost in the form of waste heat, improving overall system efficiency. Considering two possible scenarios:

1. High energy prices: When energy prices rise, the relative cost-effectiveness of TEGs improves. In industries where energy constitutes a large portion of operating expenses (e.g., cement production, steel manufacturing, or power plants), using TEGs to recover waste heat can significantly reduce overall energy costs, thereby justifying the investment in TEG technology.
2. Low energy prices: Conversely, when energy prices are low, the economic incentive to invest in TEGs diminishes. In such cases, the upfront cost of installing TEG systems may not be justified by the potential savings from waste heat recovery, particularly in industries where energy costs represent a smaller portion of operating expenses. Low energy prices reduce the urgency for businesses to optimize energy efficiency, limiting the demand for TEG solutions.

TEGs can function as a complementary technology, enhancing the energy efficiency of industrial processes that generate substantial waste heat. By capturing and converting this waste heat into usable electricity, TEGs can help offset fluctuations in energy prices and reduce overall energy costs for businesses. This serves as an important mechanism to mitigate the impact of volatile energy prices on the macroeconomic environment.

Mitigating macroeconomic volatility in TEG production

To minimize the impact of commodity and energy price volatility on the TEG industry and the broader economy, a few strategies can be employed:

- **Diversification of raw materials sources:** Developing alternative materials or sourcing from a wider range of countries can help reduce dependence on a small number of volatile markets, resulting in the stabilization of supply chains and limiting price fluctuations. This approach can involve exploring new raw material sources, establishing partnerships with suppliers in different regions, or investing in research to identify and qualify alternative materials. By using tetrahedrites seen as waste in several mining sites, START already advances this diversification need.
- **Technological advancements:** Innovations in TEG design that use more abundant and less volatile materials could mitigate the effect of commodity price swings. For example, using recycled or lower-cost semiconducting materials can help reduce reliance on scarce metals like antimony or bismuth as well as tellurium, subject of main concern addressed by the project. Ongoing research and development efforts in this area can lead to breakthroughs in material science and device engineering, making TEGs more resilient to commodity price volatility.
- **Energy efficiency in production:** Reducing the energy required for the extraction and processing of raw materials through more efficient manufacturing processes can help insulate TEG producers from fluctuations in energy prices. This can involve implementing advanced manufacturing techniques, optimizing production workflows, or exploring alternative energy sources for the production process, such as renewable energy or waste heat recovery systems.

2.1.2 Supply & Demand Trends

Supply: Tetrahedrite availability

Tetrahedrite, a more readily available material compared to traditional TE options such as tellurium and bismuth, is commonly found as a by-product in copper and silver mining. This abundance helps make the supply side more resilient to short-term fluctuations, provided mining operations maintain their current levels. Additionally, the fact that tetrahedrite is often viewed as a waste material in conventional mining operations provides a supply advantage, reducing reliance on raw material extraction. This relative abundance makes tetrahedrite an appealing choice for scalable TEGs production. However, the overall supply of tetrahedrite will depend on several key factors (Eggert, 2017):

- **Mining activity:** Tetrahedrite is typically found as a by-product in copper mining operations. Therefore, trends in copper mining, particularly the scale of mining projects and the market demand for these metals, will directly influence the availability of tetrahedrite for

thermoelectric applications. Increased mining activity and higher demand for copper could lead to greater tetrahedrite supply, making it more accessible for TEG production.

- **Processing and refining efficiency:** The ability to efficiently extract and process tetrahedrite minerals into usable forms for TEGs will also affect supply trends. If processing methods become more cost-effective and up scalable, the supply chain for tetrahedrite-based TEGs will likely strengthen. Advancements in extraction and refining techniques could help increase the supply and availability of tetrahedrite for use in TE devices.
- **Secondary resources:** Recovering and reusing tetrahedrite from waste streams or other secondary sources is a core focus of the START project, as it contributes to a more consistent and abundant supply of this mineral. Efforts to develop efficient recycling processes and establish a circular economy for tetrahedrite could further boost the availability of this material for TEG production.

Supply: Copper and antimony use

Tetrahedrite consists primarily of copper and antimony, both of which are crucial for various industrial applications (and as mentioned before classified by the EU as critical – antimony – and strategic - copper). As the demand for these metals fluctuates, it will affect the availability and cost of tetrahedrite-based TEG production.

- **Copper demand:** Copper is essential for electrical wiring, renewable energy systems, electric vehicles, and electronics. The global push towards electrification and green energy is likely to keep copper demand high, which may drive up mining activities that yield tetrahedrite as a by-product. However, rising copper demand could also increase competition for tetrahedrite resources, potentially affecting the availability for TEGs.
- **Antimony demand:** Antimony is widely used in flame retardants, batteries, and alloys. Most of the world's antimony supply comes from China, and the market can be subject to geopolitical tensions, trade policies, and production quotas, making it more vulnerable to geopolitical factors and supply chain disruptions. If demand for antimony continues to grow, this could limit the amount available for TE applications, increasing costs and potentially impacting the broader supply trend for tetrahedrite-based TEGs.

Supply: Technological advancements in TEG production

The future of tetrahedrite-based TEGs will also depend on advancements in technology. Tetrahedrite has promising TE properties, but its performance must continue to improve to compete with other materials. Research and development as well as cost effective production need to be the flagships of technological advancements.

- **Research and Development:** Ongoing R&D efforts to enhance the TE efficiency of tetrahedrites will play a crucial role in shaping their adoption in commercial TEGs. If scientists can increase energy conversion efficiency and reduce production costs, the demand for tetrahedrite as a key material in TEG production will likely grow.
- **Cost-effectiveness of production:** Tetrahedrites are generally cheaper than other thermoelectric materials like tellurium or bismuth, which may give them a competitive edge in cost-sensitive markets. As TEG technology matures and scales, the cost advantage of tetrahedrite-based devices could further boost demand.

Demand-side dynamics

The demand for tetrahedrite-based TE devices is driven by their diverse industrial applications, the increasing need for renewable energy solutions that are readily available for a wide range of environments and situations, and the broader emphasis on energy efficiency in global markets. TEGs offer unique solutions for energy harvesting and waste heat recovery across various industries. TEGs have significant potential in specialized markets that prioritize energy efficiency, decentralized power generation, and environmental sustainability. These markets provide opportunities for TE technology to thrive, particularly in environments where traditional energy solutions may not be feasible or efficient.

Demand: Combined heat and power

TEGs can be coupled in certain systems to achieve Combined Heat and Power (CHP) generation. CHP cogeneration can be deployed quickly, cost-effectively, and with few geographic limitations, benefiting several stakeholders and end-users in need of both heat and power. Key sectors include:

- Residential: Residential and community CHP or cogeneration plants can help to reduce costs and carbon emissions for residential buildings and district energy schemes.
- Industrial: Cogeneration of power and heat can be useful in industrial settings where large amounts of waste heat are produced, transforming a free resource into electricity in a unique power plant setting.

Demand: Industrial waste heat recovery

TEGs can play a pivotal role in recovering waste heat from industrial processes, converting it into electricity. Many industrial facilities generate enormous amounts of heat as a byproduct, and TEGs can efficiently capture this energy for reuse. Key sectors include:

- Steel and metal processing: Smelters, foundries, and metal refineries produce high temperatures that can be harnessed by TEGs to power machinery, reduce operational costs, and improve overall energy efficiency.
- Glass manufacturing: Furnaces in glass production emit large amounts of waste heat, making it an ideal environment for integrating TEGs to capture and reuse this energy.
- Cement production: TEGs can utilize the significant heat generated during the production process to support plant operations or sell electricity back to the grid, enhancing profitability and sustainability.

Demand: Oil and Gas industry

The Oil and Gas sector is another market where TEGs can add value by generating power in remote locations or utilizing waste heat from drilling operations, refineries and pipelines. Potential applications include:

- Remote power generation: TEGs can provide reliable, low-maintenance energy in offshore platforms, oil rigs, and pipeline stations where traditional power sources are expensive or difficult to deploy.
- Flare gas recovery: TEGs can capture heat from gas flaring—often an environmental and economic issue—and convert it into electricity, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and providing an additional energy source for the facility.

Demand: Space exploration and aerospace

TEGs have long been used in space exploration due to their ability to operate in harsh environments and generate power from the heat of radioactive decay or solar energy. Key applications include:

- Satellites and space probes: TEGs provide a dependable power source for long-term space missions where solar power may not be viable, such as in deep space probes (e.g., Voyager spacecraft).
- Aerospace: TEGs can be used to harvest heat generated by aircraft engines or spacecraft propulsion systems, offering supplemental energy for onboard electronics or other systems, improving overall energy efficiency in aerospace operations.

Demand: Military and defense

In the military and defense sectors, TEGs can provide power in remote or off-grid locations without relying on traditional fuel sources or infrastructure. Applications include:

- Portable power units: TEGs can be used in field operations to provide power for communication devices, surveillance systems, and other critical equipment. Their silent operation and low maintenance make them ideal for tactical situations.
- Unmanned systems: TEGs can be integrated into unmanned aerial vehicles, ground robots, or autonomous surveillance systems to extend operational life by harnessing waste heat or environmental thermal differences for power.

Demand: Renewable energy systems

TEGs can complement renewable energy systems, offering an additional source of power generation by converting heat into electricity. Examples include:

- Geothermal energy: TEGs can be used in geothermal power plants to capture and convert residual heat that is typically lost during the electricity generation process. This increases the efficiency of geothermal energy systems.
- Solar thermal energy: TEGs can be integrated into solar thermal plants, converting solar-generated heat into electricity. They can also be installed in solar collectors or concentrators to boost energy output, even in low-light conditions, by utilizing thermal gradients.

Demand: Marine industry

In the marine industry, TEGs can be utilized for power generation on ships and other marine vessels. Their ability to convert waste heat from engines, exhaust systems, and other heat sources into electricity makes them a valuable tool for reducing fuel consumption and improving energy efficiency on long voyages. TEGs can power critical systems, reduce reliance on fuel, and support sustainable maritime operations.

Demand: Remote and off-grid power systems

TEGs are well-suited for remote and off-grid applications, particularly in regions with limited or no access to traditional energy sources. Potential uses include:

- Rural electrification: In areas where infrastructure for conventional power grids is lacking, TEGs can provide a decentralized energy solution by harnessing waste heat from cooking stoves, biomass, or industrial processes.
- Arctic and Antarctic research stations: TEGs can provide reliable power in extreme climates, where fuel transport is costly and solar energy is intermittent or unavailable for long periods.

Demand: Consumer electronics

TEGs can be integrated into consumer electronics to provide an alternative or supplemental power source. Key applications include:

- Wearable devices: TEGs can harvest body heat to power wearable gadgets, such as smartwatches, fitness trackers, or health monitors, potentially eliminating the need for traditional batteries.
- Mobile charging solutions: TEGs can be integrated into mobile devices or portable chargers, allowing users to generate power from body heat or environmental thermal gradients, offering an eco-friendly charging alternative for phones, tablets, and other small electronics.

To remain competitive, tetrahedrite-based devices must be cost-effective, durable, and scalable. If they can offer a clear cost advantage in terms of both manufacturing and long-term operational savings, they will be better positioned to compete with more established technologies.

Specifically, these devices must be able to be produced at a low cost, withstand the rigors of their intended operating environments, and be manufactured at a scale that can meet market demand. By achieving these qualities, tetrahedrite-based TEGs can provide a compelling value proposition to industries seeking to improve their energy efficiency and reduce their environmental impact.

2.1.3 Economic value of TEGs

Studies on TE materials suggest that innovative manufacturing methods can improve the economic feasibility of TE devices. While tetrahedrite-based materials were not included in their analysis, the cost-effectiveness of these devices largely depends on the performance of the TE modules and their production costs (LeBlanc et al., 2014).

The key parameters to evaluate economic value for TEGs are (Benday et al., 2017; Narducci et al., 2017):

- Net present value (NPV): The NPV of using TEGs for energy recovery is highly dependent on factors such as ore prices, production costs, and operational uptime. Given the relatively low costs of repurposing waste materials, the potential returns are promising.
- Productivity: The technology offers a cost-effective method for generating electricity from waste, although production rates of energy from waste heat may be lower compared to traditional energy sources. However, the low operational costs and minimal environmental impact offset this limitation, can make TEGs economically viable.
- Operational effectiveness: TEG technology is particularly well-suited for industries that generate significant waste heat, such as metallurgy, glass manufacturing, and cement production. The potential for energy savings in these sectors can significantly improve overall productivity and reduce operational expenses.

Cost-effective manufacturing

The production of tetrahedrite-based TEGs benefits from advancements in manufacturing processes can help streamline costs. Unlike more traditional TEG materials that require complex and expensive production methods, tetrahedrites are relatively easy to process, leading to lower production and refinement costs.

- **Simplified processing:** Tetrahedrite-based TEGs do not require rare earth elements or toxic materials, which often drive up costs in alternative technologies. Instead, the manufacturing process for tetrahedrites can be optimized with existing infrastructure, reducing the need for specialized, costly procedures.
- **Scalability:** With improvements in research and development, tetrahedrite-based TEGs can be produced at scale with relatively low incremental costs, creating economies of scale. The scalability of these devices offers a competitive edge in various markets, especially as industries look for cost-effective ways to harness waste heat or generate decentralized power.

Long-term cost savings

Although initial investments in TEG technology may require upfront capital expenditure, tetrahedrite-based systems provide long-term economic benefits through energy savings and reduced operational costs.

- **Energy efficiency and cost reduction:** By converting waste heat into electricity, tetrahedrite-based TEGs can improve energy efficiency in industrial and residential applications, leading to lower overall energy consumption. This results in cost savings on energy bills for businesses and consumers alike.
- **Durability and low maintenance:** Tetrahedrite-based TEGs are designed to be robust and durable, with minimal maintenance requirements over their operational life. Unlike traditional energy systems, which often require frequent repairs or replacement parts, TEGs can offer a longer service life, further enhancing their economic value by reducing long-term operational costs.

Potential Added Value & Cost Competitiveness from a Raw Materials Perspective

A simple price analysis can help determine the opportunity costs of producing tetrahedrite-based TE modules and systems compared to benchmark devices or selling the materials outright. Using a representative elemental composition of a tetrahedrite-rich sulphide (Awe, 2010) and average prices for the respective metals, it's possible to estimate the potential revenue for selling the metals per kilogram of tetrahedrite (Table 1).

A comparative analysis of the costs of producing tetrahedrite-based devices versus selling raw materials can shed light on their potential value. A price analysis of tetrahedrite's key components—copper, antimony, zinc, and iron—reveals that the potential revenue from selling the raw metals is around \$6.53 per kilogram of tetrahedrite. There is not much information on the production of tetrahedrite-based TE devices, but data from Jacobs (2014) suggests that the production cost of tetrahedrite-based TE devices can be as low as \$4 per kilogram, significantly cheaper than the \$24–146 per kilogram price range of other thermoelectric materials.

Table 1: Composition of a tetrahedrite-rich sulphide and potential revenue by selling its metals.

	<i>Composition</i>	<i>Price</i>	<i>Revenue per kg of tetrahedrite</i>
<i>Element</i>	%	\$/kg	\$/kg-TH
<i>Cu</i>	29.6	8.99 ¹	2.66
<i>Fe</i>	24.5	0.10 ²	0.025
<i>Zn</i>	31.7	3.09 ³	0.98
<i>Sb</i>	10.8	25.00 ⁴	2.7
<i>As</i>	3.5	4.52 ⁵	0.16
		Total	6.53

This pricing advantage suggests that the production of tetrahedrite-based thermoelectric devices can offer higher economic returns compared to simply selling the raw materials, particularly when scaled for industrial applications.

2.1.4 Environmental Impact of TEGs

Traditional TE devices often rely on materials that are toxic, rare, or expensive, which limits their widespread use (Jacobs, 2014). In contrast, tetrahedrite-based devices offer a more environmentally friendly alternative, using abundant materials that are relatively less harmful to produce. This enables industries to more easily comply with environmental policies and sustainability regulations set by governments, particularly as global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions intensify. For example, wide implementation of TE devices could contribute to countries meeting their energy targets and thus supporting world policies such as the Paris Agreement. Tetrahedrite-based TE devices can also help industries transition towards low-carbon production processes, further supporting the global energy transition, by using waste heat and abundant materials. The tetrahedrite-based TEGs present several key economic and environmental advantages:

- **Energy efficiency:** The technology taps into waste heat from industrial processes, providing a cost-effective way to generate electricity. This reduces reliance on traditional energy sources and supports the transition to a more sustainable energy infrastructure.
- **Resource efficiency:** The use of mining byproducts for energy production reduces the need for new mineral extraction, lowering the environmental footprint and contributing to the circular economy.
- **Lower carbon emissions:** By converting waste heat into usable energy, TEGs help reduce overall carbon emissions, contributing to global sustainability goals and compliance with climate-related regulations. The effects of different energy sources on carbon emissions and environmental sustainability are analyzed, including evaluating how TEGs or renewable sources contribute to reducing the grid's overall carbon footprint, improving long-term sustainability.

¹ <https://www.dailymetalprice.com/copper.html>

² <https://www.dailymetalprice.com/iron-ore.html>

³ <https://www.dailymetalprice.com/zinc.html>

⁴ <https://finance.yahoo.com/news/antimony-prices-surged-200-2024-000000532.html>

⁵ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/797487/us-arsenic-average-price/>

Energy transition trends

The global shift towards clean energy and decarbonization is a key macroeconomic trend that will likely boost demand for energy-efficient technologies like TEGs. As countries strive to meet their climate targets under international agreements such as the Paris Agreement, industries are being pushed to adopt technologies that lower their energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.

Tetrahedrite-based TE devices are well-positioned to benefit from these trends, especially in sectors where waste heat recovery can contribute to carbon-neutral operations. The focus on circular economy models, where waste products are reused or repurposed, further enhances the value proposition of TEGs as they can convert waste heat—an otherwise lost resource—into usable energy. By tapping into this abundant source of waste heat, tetrahedrite-based TEGs can help industries improve their energy efficiency, reduce their carbon footprint, and contribute to the broader transition towards a more sustainable and decarbonized economy.

2.1.5 Policy, Regulations and Investment Considerations

The growth and adoption of tetrahedrite-based TEGs are strongly influenced by national and international policies, regulatory frameworks, and investment landscapes. As the world transitions towards more sustainable energy systems and seeks to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, governments and industry stakeholders have a crucial role to play in shaping the future of emerging technologies like TEGs. This section outlines the key policy and regulatory drivers, the role of government incentives, and the investment considerations for promoting tetrahedrite-based TEGs.

Government policies and regulations

Government policies are instrumental in creating a conducive environment for the development and commercialization of TEG technologies. Policies aimed at promoting renewable energy, energy efficiency, and waste heat recovery are particularly relevant to the adoption of tetrahedrite-based TEGs.

- **Renewable Energy and Climate Policies:** Many countries have implemented policies that prioritize the adoption of clean and renewable energy technologies to meet global climate goals. National energy policies that set targets for reducing carbon emissions, increasing the share of renewables in the energy mix, and improving energy efficiency directly support the deployment of TEGs. By converting waste heat into electricity and improving the overall energy efficiency of industrial processes, tetrahedrite-based TEGs can contribute to meeting these targets.
- **Waste heat recovery regulations:** In the EU there are regulatory instruments mentioning the reduction of industrial waste heat emissions, such as the Directive (EU) 2023/1791. Regulations such as this and similar ones, often part of broader energy efficiency initiatives, encourage industries to adopt technologies that recover and utilize waste heat. Tetrahedrite-based TEGs, as an effective waste heat recovery solution, stand to benefit from such regulations, especially in sectors like manufacturing, power generation, and data centers.
- **Environmental compliance and Emission Reduction Standards:** Regulations aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions are becoming more stringent, particularly in energy-intensive industries. Businesses and industries that fail to comply with emission reduction targets may face penalties, while those that adopt energy-efficient technologies, such as

TEGs, could benefit from incentives or avoid penalties. Tetrahedrite-based TEGs can support compliance with these environmental standards by reducing the carbon footprint of industrial processes.

Incentives and subsidies

Government incentives and subsidies can play a critical role in accelerating the adoption of tetrahedrite-based TEGs. These financial mechanisms lower the cost of investment and encourage industries to adopt innovative technologies.

- **Tax incentives and credits:** Governments often provide tax incentives, such as investment tax credits or production tax credits, for companies that invest in clean energy technologies. Tetrahedrite-based TEGs, as part of waste heat recovery systems or renewable energy projects, may qualify for these incentives, making them more financially attractive to investors and businesses. Tax credits can offset the initial capital costs, thereby enhancing the economic feasibility of TEG deployment.
- **Subsidies for clean energy products:** In many countries, governments offer direct subsidies for the adoption of energy-efficient and renewable technologies. These subsidies can take the form of grants, low-interest loans, or rebates. Tetrahedrite-based TEG projects could benefit from such subsidies, particularly in industries that are mandated to reduce waste heat emissions or improve energy efficiency.
- **R&D grants:** Government funding for research and development (R&D) is essential for advancing TEG technology. Grants aimed at developing new materials, improving TEG efficiency, and scaling up production processes can help reduce the costs and accelerate the commercialization of tetrahedrite-based TEGs. Collaborative R&D initiatives between governments, academic institutions, and private industry are critical for driving innovation in this field.

Investment considerations

The economic viability of tetrahedrite-based TEGs depends on various factors, including market demand, the cost of raw materials, the maturity of the technology, and the investment environment, as mentioned before.

From an investment point of view, public and private investors need to carefully consider the following factors when evaluating the potential of TEGs as a long-term energy solution:

- **Cost of tetrahedrite-based materials:** Tetrahedrite, as a naturally abundant and cost-effective material, provides a competitive edge in terms of production costs. However, fluctuations in the prices of metals that are key components of tetrahedrite (such as copper and antimony) could impact the overall cost structure of TEG production, if their prices rise. Investors should monitor commodity market trends and assess the long-term availability and pricing of these materials when considering TEG investments.
- **Technology maturity and scalability:** While TEG technology has made significant advancements, tetrahedrite-based TEGs are still emerging in the market. The maturity of the technology and its scalability will play a critical role in attracting investment. Investors need to evaluate the readiness of the technology for large-scale deployment, the potential for cost reductions through improved manufacturing processes, and the competitive landscape relative to other energy technologies.

- Return on Investment (ROI) and Payback period: Investors are likely to focus on the expected ROI and payback period for tetrahedrite-based TEG projects. The economic attractiveness of TEGs will depend on their ability to generate savings through waste heat recovery and provide consistent power generation in decentralized energy systems. Investors should also consider the potential for long-term cost savings from reduced energy consumption and improved energy efficiency.
- Market demand and growth potential: The demand for energy-efficient and sustainable technologies is growing, driven by the global shift toward renewable energy and decarbonization. Investors should consider the market potential for tetrahedrite-based TEGs in industries with significant waste heat output, such as manufacturing, power generation, and transportation. The growth of the circular economy and the increasing importance of energy efficiency will likely drive demand for TEGs in the coming years.

Risks and Challenges

Despite the potential benefits, investors and policymakers should be aware of the risks and challenges associated with tetrahedrite-based TEGs:

- Policy uncertainty: Changes in government policies, especially regarding renewable energy targets, carbon pricing, and subsidies, can create uncertainty for investors. A sudden shift in policy direction could impact the financial viability of TEG projects. Investors should closely monitor regulatory developments and engage in policy advocacy to promote favorable conditions for TEG adoption.
- Technological competition: Tetrahedrite-based TEGs will need to compete with other energy technologies, such as photovoltaic solar panels, wind turbines, and other waste heat recovery systems. The ability of TEGs to carve out a niche in the market will depend on their cost-effectiveness, efficiency, and ease of integration into existing energy systems.
- Commodity price volatility: Sudden price fluctuations in metals such as copper and antimony could impact the production cost of TEGs and influence their overall economic competitiveness. Mitigating strategies, such as securing long-term supply agreements or developing alternative materials, may help address this challenge.

The successful adoption of tetrahedrite-based TEGs will depend on a combination of supportive government policies, financial incentives, and a favorable investment environment. Clear regulations promoting waste heat recovery, energy efficiency, and environmental sustainability will help drive demand for TEG technologies. At the same time, government subsidies, tax incentives, and R&D funding will lower the barriers to entry and encourage innovation in TEG production. For investors, the key considerations will include the cost of raw materials, the maturity and scalability of the technology, and the long-term economic benefits of waste heat recovery and energy efficiency. While challenges such as policy uncertainty and commodity price volatility exist, the growing demand for sustainable energy solutions positions tetrahedrite-based TEGs as an attractive investment in the renewable energy landscape.

2.1.6 Conclusion on Macroeconomics

Tetrahedrite-based TEGs present a promising solution in the evolving energy landscape, particularly in addressing the challenges of waste heat recovery and sustainable power generation. Throughout this sub-chapter, numerous factors that influence the viability and future of tetrahedrite-

based TEGs were presented and analysed, including their economic potential, market dynamics, policy influences, and technological scalability.

The macroeconomic implications of adopting tetrahedrite-based TEGs highlight both the opportunities and challenges inherent in such a transition. The abundant and relatively inexpensive nature of tetrahedrite — comprised primarily of copper and antimony — positions these TEGs as a cost-effective alternative to traditional materials, offering competitive advantages in production and price stability. The stable and predictable nature of the energy sources TEGs exploit, such as industrial waste heat and other constant heat sources, simplifies their integration into existing power grids compared to more intermittent renewable technologies like solar and wind.

However, like all emerging technologies, the widespread adoption of tetrahedrite-based TEGs will be heavily dependent on the regulatory environment, investment landscape, and policy support. Clear, well-crafted government policies aimed at promoting renewable energy, enhancing energy efficiency, and regulating waste heat emissions will be vital for driving demand. Incentives such as tax credits, subsidies, and R&D grants will help lower the cost of production and encourage private sector investment.

Economic considerations also play a key role. The market for copper and antimony, key constituents of tetrahedrite, is relatively stable but subject to commodity price fluctuations that could impact the cost of production. Furthermore, the energy price environment will directly affect the competitiveness of TEGs, particularly in comparison to other energy technologies such as solar photovoltaics and wind turbines.

In terms of supply trends, the availability of tetrahedrite-rich ores is robust, making this material a feasible and scalable option for TEG production. As energy efficiency becomes more critical across industries, the potential for TEGs to carve out a niche in areas like industrial waste heat recovery, data centers, and power plants will grow, driving broader market adoption.

The path forward for tetrahedrite-based TEGs involves not just technological innovation but a strong alignment with environmental and economic policies that support sustainable energy solutions. If policies continue to promote clean energy, coupled with increased investment in research and development, these devices could play a crucial role in the future energy ecosystem by offering an efficient, low-cost, and environmentally friendly way to capture and reuse waste heat.

Tetrahedrite-based TEGs hold significant promise for contributing to a greener, more energy-efficient future. Their economic value, regulatory backing, and technological advantages offer substantial potential for reducing emissions, enhancing energy efficiency, and providing a reliable source of decentralized power generation. With continued innovation and policy support, tetrahedrite-based TEGs could play an integral role in the global transition to a more sustainable energy system.

2.2 COMPETITION AND BENCHMARKING

Analysing the state-of-the-art, potential market competition and benchmarking along the START value chain are all essential steps and help the determination of potential business and commercial feasibility factors for the tetrahedrite-based TE devices and systems that will be created within the START ecosystem.

Competition and benchmarking analysis were performed at different levels. First, a comparison was made on the basis of electricity generation technologies, followed by a comparison made for

technologies and systems transforming heat into electricity. Finally, a comparison is presented with other TE materials and TE devices.

2.2.1 Competition in electricity generation

TEGs are designed to generate electricity from a difference in heat, which would entail that they are direct competitors to other electricity generation technologies, especially ones that also use waste heat. Here, it is assumed that competition is not seen between TE and other renewable energy sources. This stems from the currently reduced and targeted amount of electricity generated with the use of TEGs.

The following technologies are commonly used to generate electricity: solar, wind, hydropower, geothermal, nuclear power, biomass, coal, waves, gas, fuel cells. All of them have positive aspects as well as drawbacks. In current times, renewable energy sources are favoured to other sources such as fossil fuels. TEGs themselves can be seen as renewable (green) energy sources (Mamur et al., 2021), already showing an advantage when compared against the use of fossil fuels for electricity generation.

TEGs are not able to generate great amounts of electricity when compared to other more mature technologies. As an example, in the USA, in 2023, about 4,178 billion⁶ kilowatthours (kWh) of electricity were generated at electricity generation facilities (US Energy Information Administration). From this amount, renewables accounted for 894 billion kWh. In the EU, in 2022, total net electricity generation was 2 701 TWh, with wind, hydro and solar used to produce 34.3% of the net electricity generated⁷.

There is no easy-to-find data on the use of TEGs for energy production stemming from their sparse use, with most data being found in research papers. In one of these, Champier (2017) states that TEGs used in recovery of waste heat in industries could generate as much as 136MWh annually. For TEGs to have a greater representation in terms of electricity generated they would need to be widely implemented, while still competing with some of the RES previously listed.

Therefore, TEGs do not threaten/compete against the wide implementation of these technologies (e.g. solar or wind). They do, however, perform in niche markets, which is a unique value proposition. The ideal situation would be where TEGs are integrated with these other greener sources to produce even more electricity in one coupled system. Therefore, TEGs can be seen as a technology line complementary to solar, wind and even use of batteries. The complementation aspect can be looked at from two temperature perspectives:

- For high temperatures (kW scale)
 - Through waste heat recovery to reduce the amount of energy needed.
 - Through micro-CHP to reduce the fluctuations of solar and wind at the supply side.
- For low temperatures (W scale)
 - Powering sensors and IoT in general does support smart and energy efficient process control.

⁶ 1,000 million

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Electricity_production,_consumption_and_market_overview

As a good example, Mamur et al. (2021) provide information on an integrated TEG system with CHP approaches.

2.2.2 *Comparison and benchmarking to technologies and systems transforming heat into electricity*

While not facing competition against the previously mentioned, more eclectic, energy sources, TEGs face direct competition from other technologies that also transform waste heat into electricity/power. Recently, more R&D has been poured into technologies and systems transforming waste heat into power, due to the great amount of waste heat that is produced in several industries. Achieving good efficiency through these technologies is a great way to improve energy efficiency, reduce environmental impact and boost the use of RES.

The following technologies range in their development state (different TRL levels and thus technology maturity). Also, their energy output can be also highly variant in scale (mW – W - kW and MW). In one way or the other, they offer competition for the implementation of TEGs now and in a near to long-term future. These technologies need to be monitored for their state-of-the-art, development and applications.

Mature (incumbent) technologies (from TRL 7 to 9)

- Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC): ORC systems use an organic fluid with a lower boiling point (e.g. water, ammonia) to convert lower temperature waste heat into energy. They are power cycle systems used to convert low-to-medium temperature waste heat. These systems have four main components in the expander (turbine), condenser, pump and evaporator. ORC are commonly used in geothermal plants, biomass plants, industrial waste heat recovery and solar thermal power generation. Development of these systems towards higher efficiencies has been granted with the help of improved working fluids and turbine technologies, making them one of the favoured technologies in the waste heat recovery and use spectrum.
- Stirling Engine: This is a closed regenerative gas cycle that compresses and then expands gas (e.g. hydrogen, helium) in between hot & cold sources, converting heat into mechanical power. Stirling engine systems are used in solar power systems, biomass boilers, industrial processes, submarines and aircrafts.
- Phase Change Material Systems: Materials (e.g. paraffin) absorb and release energy during phase changes, for example changes from solid to liquid state of materials. Expansion and contraction are captured in a hydraulic system and converted into electricity, with waste heat used to trigger the change of phases. Used in thermal storage systems, CHP and industrial processes with waste heat. Research focuses on integrating Phase Change Materials with thermoelectric systems or using them for waste heat recovery in small-scale applications.

Novel technologies (from TRL 1 to 6)

- Thermionic converters: These systems use electrons from a heated material that are then captured on a cooler surface, generating an electrical current. They are primarily used in high-temperature applications including nuclear reactors. Ongoing work aims to improve the efficiency and lifespan of these systems for terrestrial use in industries with high-temperature processes.

- **Thermophotovoltaics generators:** These systems are used to convert infrared radiation, in the form of heat, using photovoltaic cells. Thermal radiation, emitted from high temperature materials, is captured by photovoltaic cells, therefore their application is limited to high temperature waste heat. They are used in industrial furnaces, glass and steel plants. For this technology, research is currently leading to better materials for energy transformation.
- **Piezoelectric Energy Harvesting:** This technology uses piezoelectric materials to generate electrical charges from mechanical stresses caused by differences in temperatures. It is commonly used for vibration energy harvesting, but some applications (e.g. industrial processes) use waste heat thermal expansion to generate energy. Research focus is on the development of better high-temperature piezoelectric materials.
- **Supercritical CO₂ power cycles:** These systems use CO₂ in a supercritical state to drive a turbine, converting high temperature waste heat into electricity, and are applied in high temperature power plants and industrial processes.
- **Thermo Magnetic Generators:** These systems convert heat (temperature changes) into electricity by using the thermomagnetic effect, a phenomenon where certain materials change their magnetic properties in response to temperature variations. They can be used to convert waste heat into electricity in industrial processes and engines where the temperature of the waste heat fluctuates.

Table 2 offers a comparison, taking into account relevant viability parameters, between TE and other mature waste heat technologies.

Table 2: Comparison of mature technologies and systems transforming waste heat into power, in which thermoelectrics is included.

Technology	Size and weight	Efficiency and capacity	Pros	Cons	Applications
Thermoelectric generators	Few to 40 cm or more Few to several grams	5-10 % efficiency mW to KW energy production	Solid state, No moving parts, Versatility, Reliability, Low maintenance, High energy density	High payback time, If commercial, they include toxic elements	Space missions, Industrial waste heat, Micro-CHP
Organic Rankine Cycle	From 1 m ³ to 100 m ³ Few to several kg, even tonnes	10-20 % efficiency kW to MW energy production	Adaptable to several heat sources, High TRL, Reliability, Continuous operation	High cost in low temperature range, Use of flammable and/or toxic gases	Industrial waste heat, Geothermal, Biomass
Stirling Engine	Few centimeters to few meters From 1 kg to 1 tonne	20-40 % efficiency W to kW energy production	High efficiency, Low maintenance need, Reliable	Mechanically complex, Not viable below 100 °C, Low specific power, Large	Space applications, Small-scale heat-to-power

Table 2 (continued).

Technology	Size and weight	Efficiency and capacity	Pros	Cons	Applications
Phase Change Material Systems	Few cm to few m From 500 grams to few kilograms	70-90 % efficiency 100 kW to 1 MW energy production	Recovery of very low temperature waste heat	Requires liquid hot and cold sources	Building thermal management, Industrial application

Table 3 offers a comparison, taking into account relevant viability parameters, between novel technologies waste heat technologies.

Table 3: Comparison of novel and still in research-state technologies and systems transforming waste heat into power.

Technology	Size and weight	Efficiency and capacity	Pros	Cons	Applications
Thermophotovoltaics generators	Few centimeters to 1.5 m or more Few grams to 50 kg and more	5-15 % efficiency W to kW of energy production	Versatility, Compactness, Direct energy conversion	Materials used, Complex design, Heat management challenges, High costs	Powering sensors and electronics, Industrial applications or integrated into concentrated solar power systems
Piezoelectric Energy Harvesting	From millimeters to few centimeter Few grams up to 2 kg	5-30 % efficiency MicroW to mW energy production	Low maintenance, Compactness, Environmentally friendly materials	Low power output, Complex, material limitations, Dependent on the environment	Powering sensors, wearables, and IoT devices, Industrial applications
Thermionic converters	Few millimeters to few centimeter Few grams to few kilos	5-20 % efficiency W to kW power production	Direct energy conversion, High temperature range of operation, versatility	Complex, Costly, Limited commercial deployment	Space, Waste heat recovery
Supercritical CO ₂ power cycles	From 1-2 m ³ to 30 m ³ and more Few to several tonnes	40-50 % efficiency 1 to 100 MW energy production	High efficiency, Compactness	Material challenges, Complex, Potential CO ₂ leakage	Geothermal and Solar Thermal, Waste heat recovery
Thermo Magnetic Generators	From 5 cm to 40 cm Few grams to few kilos	1-5 % efficiency From mW to kW energy production	Few moving components	Low energy density, Low efficiency	Early-stage research, Waste heat recovery

TEGs face different levels of competition against these technologies. First, a comparison must be made regarding the more mature technologies, the ones that might offer competition to thermoelectric technology in the current to near-future timeframes. TEGs face this competition from the Organic Rankine Cycle, Stirling Engine and Phase Change Material Systems. The following conclusions can be listed:

- The Organic Rankine Cycle is the only technology capable of producing energy in the magnitude of MW, having a clear advantage on situations where high amount of energy can be produced and/or is needed. The use case is totally different from TEG applications.
- Thermoelectrics compete with the Stirling Engine for energy production at the kW scale. Stirling engines are more efficient but also have bigger size and weight than TEGs, which are factors needed to be considering when choosing one or the other technology.
- Phase Change Material Systems are only valid for <200 °C, which are low temperatures. Despite their very high energy production efficiency and the amount of energy they can generate, the limitation on the operating temperature, will limit their application against the TEGs case.
- One distinct advantage of TEG is the use of benign and available materials. In the specific case of START, materials are available in Europe. They also have low maintenance and long-life character. TEGs are one of the few technology lines with no moving parts, while still presenting versatility and reliability as well as low maintenance needs in their current and future potential applications.
- While more established technologies such as the ORC show clear advantages, TEGs still have potential for wider implementation. They are smaller and lighter than some of the competition, while still having good efficiency and energy production considering the size and weight of the system.

Then, it is necessary to have a closer look at upcoming competition for the mid to long-term timeframes. The studied technologies, which are currently at a lower TRL, will become more mature and enter the market offering competition to TEGs. Listed lower TRL technologies include Thermophotovoltaics generators, Piezoelectric Energy Harvesting, Thermionic converters, Supercritical CO₂ power cycles and Thermo Magnetic Generators. The following conclusions can be listed:

- Thermoelectrics technologies compete with Piezoelectric energy harvesting and Thermomagnetic generators at mW scale. They show similar size and weight as TEGs and their use cases are also comparable. Competition between these technologies will end up being tied to the positives and negatives of each tech – however, even their pros and cons share similarities. TEG technology has the advantage of being the most mature of these technologies.
- Thermophotovoltaic generators and Thermionic converters are only used for >1000 °C, which are temperatures outside the range of operation for thermoelectrics. Therefore, they offer no direct competition to TEGs.
- Supercritical CO₂ power cycles produce high amounts of energy – in the scale of MW of energy – completely outclassing TEGs. Supercritical CO₂ power cycles will be tied to specific conditions where high amounts of energy are needed, since their size, weight and materials will set them back in situations where the energy requirements and/or needs are lower.

Ultimately, favourability for the use of TE technologies against some of the discussed competition will be influenced by the final application as well as industrial feasibility and economic feasibility of the solutions. The value chains presented in Chapters 3 shed light on this potential.

2.2.3 Competition within TEGs materials and devices

TEG-based systems and devices are already on the market, challenging the START technologies for competition. Several companies involved in the production of TEGs were studied and some of their flagship products analysed. A (non-extensive) list of these companies is included below. Information on these companies was obtained with the help of search engines and by visiting the companies' websites.

- [Align Sourcing](#) (USA)
- [ATS](#) (USA)
- [Beijing Huimao Cooling Co., Ltd](#) (China)
- [Bentek Systems](#) (Canada)
- [Cidete Ingenieros SL](#) (Spain)
- [Coherent Corp](#) (USA)
- [Crystal](#) (Russia)
- [Custom thermoelectric](#) (USA)
- [Ecogen Technology](#) (Russia)
- [Eureca](#) (Germany)
- [European Thermodynamics](#) (UK)
- [Everredtronics Ltd](#) (China)
- [Ferrotec](#) (USA)
- [Gentherm](#) (USA)
- [Global Power Technologies](#) (Canada)
- [GreenTEG AG](#) (Switzerland)
- [Hi-Z Technology Inc](#) (USA)
- [KELK](#) (Japan)
- [Kryotherm](#) (Russia)
- [Laird Thermal Systems](#) (China)
- [Merit Technology Group](#) (China)
- [Micropelt](#) (Germany)
- [Quick Ohm](#) (Germany)
- [S&PF Modul](#) (Ukraine)
- [TEC Microsystems](#) (Germany)
- [TECTEG MFR](#) (Canada)
- [Termo-Gen AB](#) (Sweden)
- [Wellen Tech](#) (China)
- [P&N Tech](#) (China)
- [TEGMA](#) (Norway)

A quick glance at the list shows that several TEG producing companies are located outside of Europe – some of these with branches in European territory (e.g. Laird Thermal Systems). TEG companies in Europe are still considerable in number, with most of them in Germany. Of the 30 companies listed, 10 are from European countries. These represent 33% of the analysis, showcasing the R&D efforts being put into TE development towards (successful) commercialisation of TEGs.

Table 4 introduces a comparison of upcoming START TEGs and a few selected competitors' TEGs. Several operational parameters may be used for comparison. The most relevant factors and indicators are listed including the type of materials used, the operating temperature of the devices (also dictating their application), the efficiency and power output, and finally, the features and advantages. Information on competitors was taken from their respective product pages and, in some instances, information on parameters was missing, thus not included in the analysis.

Table 4: Comparison of START TEGs and a few selected competitors' TEGs.

	Type	Operating temperature range	Efficiency	Power output	Application	Features/Advantages
START TEG (RGS)	p-type: tetrahedrite n-type: MgSb	200 °C - 400 °C	4-7 %	W-kW scale	Residential and Industrial use	Uses widely available materials; Focus on sustainability of resources
START TEG (TEGnology)	P-type: ZnSb n-type: MgSb	RT-300 °C	Up to 12 %	mW to kW	Sensors and electronics, PV panels	Flexible and bendable, easy to up-scale, inexpensive to manufacture, compatible with different material systems.
Custom Thermoelectric (2411G-7L31-15CX1)⁸	Bismuth telluride	Max 320 °C	Not available	22 W	Residential waste heat recovery	Small size for compact power generation, Both sides of this TEG have a graphite foil pre-applied as a thermal interface material, Lapped ceramic (Al ₂ O ₃) faces
Align Sourcing (G-127-14-16-L-S)⁹	Bismuth telluride	Max 200 °C	Not available	2.42 W	Industrial sensors	Optimized for power generation; High reliability construction and nickel barrier for long TEG life
CIDETE Ingenieros (CID-PGM-32-62)¹⁰	Skutterudites	220 °C	2.8 %	23.5 W	Waste heat recovery	Use of Skutterudites
Crystal (H-288-14-06)¹¹	Bismuth telluride	150 °C - 200 °C	4.2 %	15.7 W	Industrial sensors	Options for adding lapping, ceramic metallization, pre-tinning and silicon sealing
Ecogen (Mars-35)¹²	Bismuth telluride	500 °C	6.2 %	35 W	Heat recovery from vehicle engines, Autonomous power supply of automation and remote-control systems	Thermoelectric generators with a heat source providing heat flow of approximately 1 kW of a heat power through the module
Eureca (TEG2-50-50-40/200)¹³	Bismuth telluride	Max 200 °C	Not available	40 W	Power generation using waste heat of combustors or solar panels	Not available
European Thermodynamics (GM250-127-28-12)¹⁴	Bismuth telluride	250 °C	Not available	25.5 W	Sensors and other low power electronics in most types of industrial applications	Compact structure (no moving parts); Reliable performance; Maintenance-free; Noise-free operation; Low-carbon green technology

⁸ https://customthermoelectric.com/media/wysiwyg/TEG_spec_sheets/2411G-7L31-15CX1_20140508_spec_sht.pdf

⁹ <https://thermoelectric.alignsourcing.com/item/thermoelectric-generators-and-assemblies-teg-/thermoelectric-generators-teg-g-127-14-16-l-s>

¹⁰ https://www.cidete.com/images/CID-PGM-32-62_CIDETE.pdf

¹¹ https://crystaltherm.com/images/Katalogi/Crystal_catalogue_TEM.pdf

¹² <https://ecogenthermoelectric.com/mars-35.html>

¹³ https://www.eureca.de/files/pdf/cooling/teg/TEG2-50-50-40_200.pdf

¹⁴ <https://www.adaptivete.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/GM250-127-28-12.pdf>

Table 4 (continued).

	Type	Operating temperature range	Efficiency	Power output	Application	Features/Advantages
Hi-Z (HZ-20HV)¹⁵	Bismuth telluride	350 °C	2.7 - 4 %	24.3 W	High power thermoelectric power generation system that needs a large number of 'trouble-free' modules	Rugged Construction (no brittle structural ceramic, no solders, fiber glass reinforced framework tolerant to abuse); Long lifetime (~4-6 % annual power degradation @ Th = 230 °C); Not vulnerable to thermal shock or quick thermal cycling
P&N Tech (TEG-127020)¹⁶	Bismuth telluride	Max 225 °C	Not available	8.5 W	Various environments where hard to get or unsuitable for electrical power, and the excess or waste heat recycling fields	Working time more than 100 K hours; Long-term working temperature is recommended to be below 225 °C
S&PF Modul (MTG 2-0,8-199DT2)¹⁷	Bismuth telluride	200 °C	4 %	11 W	Industrial sensors	Not available

The comparison above highlights some key differences between the TEGs developed within START and some TEGs available commercially. A key aspect lies in the use of tetrahedrite as the p-type thermoelement, resulting in advantages in terms of potential costs and sustainability when compared to other TEGs that mainly use bismuth telluride in their composition, a highly toxic and rare element. Similarly to some of the analysed competitors, START TEG devices operate in mid-temperature ranges and despite of using tetrahedrite instead of the bismuth telluride material, START TEGs showcase competitive power output and better efficiency. The application and features of the TEG products are also similar, since these stem from the technology itself. START TEGs have two unique advantages: they use widely available materials and there is a focus on sustainability of resources. These aspects are only matched by the TEG from Cidete Ingenieros which uses Skutterudites, also a sustainable and widely available material.

Materials used in the creation of TEGs is indeed a very relevant topic. Bismuth telluride is the clear winner in terms of commercial applications but is facing rising competition (as seen from the R&D into new materials) from other sources that are less costly, less influenced by exports and more sustainable. One of these options is tetrahedrite, but there are others as shown in Table 5 (Fu et al., 2018; Carlini et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2020; Finn et al., 2021; Cook, 2022; d'Angelo et al., 2023).

¹⁵ <https://hi-z.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Data-Sheet-HZ-20HV-1.pdf>

¹⁶ <http://www.pengnantech.com/power-generator-teg-127020.html>

¹⁷ <https://spf-modul.com/en/products-en/thermoelectric-generators-teg.html>

Table 5: Comparison of START TE materials with conventional TE materials.

	Material type	Efficiency/ZT	Operating temperature range (°C)	Advantages	Disadvantages	Applications
Tetrahedrites (as used in the START case - RGS)	Antimony based	4-7 %	200-400 °C	Abundantly available, cheap and benign raw materials	Limited to low-temperature applications; Performance degrades at higher temperatures	Waste heat recovery; Small-scale power generation
Tetrahedrites (as used in the START case - TEGnology)	Antimony based	4-7 %	200-400 °C	Abundant and largely available on the global landscape.	Big variations in performance, depending on the origin of the mineral. Inconstancy in composition causes challenges in manufacturing and assembling.	Waste heat recovery; Small-scale power generation
Skutterudites	CoSb ₃	Max ZT = 2 in lab	RT to 550 °C	Elemental abundance, Good mechanical properties	Complexity of fabrication; Large number of possible compositions results in different ZT	Automotive; Waste heat recovery; Aerospace
Half-Heusler Alloys	NbFeSb	Max ZT = 1 in lab	RT – 800 °C	Elemental abundance, Excellent electrical properties, Mechanical robustness, Good thermal stability	Achieving high ZT values is hindered by high contact resistance	No commercial application yet
Silicon–Germanium	SiGe	Max ZT = 0.6 in lab	300 – 1000 °C	Relative ease in preparing n-type and p-type semiconductors; Good performance at high temperature	Expensive, Heavy	Aerospace; High-temperature industrial processes
Chalcogenides	Bi ₂ Te ₃	ZT up to 2.4 in lab	RT – 300 °C	Most widely deployed; Best performing at room temperature	Concerns about the long-term availability of tellurium; Toxicity of tellurium	Cooling; Waste heat recovery
	PbTe	Max ZT = 2.5 in lab	RT to 450 °C	Shows both p-type behavior and n-type behavior; Good performance at medium temperatures	Concerns about the long-term availability of tellurium; Toxicity of tellurium and lead	Automotive; Aerospace

Similarly to the importance of monitoring the development of other waste heat recovery technologies and to monitoring other TEGs, it is also highly relevant to analyse the development of materials used in the devices themselves.

2.3 THE START VALUE CHAIN AND SUPPLY CHAIN APPROACH

As a project looking into continuous technological development, commercialization and further exploitation of its unique devices and technological driver, START needs to create an industrial viability assessment coupled with economic studies that can showcase, evaluate and benchmark the START technology components against conventional solutions for generating energy.

START creates both a new value and supply chains, stemming from the innovative use of waste minerals in the composition and assembly of TEGs and corresponding energy-producing systems. Despite these being specialised and tailored depending on their application, general approaches for both chains can be detailed. The aim is that this general approach can be used by any application to define their own value and supply chains.

The generic value chain and supply chain approach, highlights the potential value of the START project, which is then deepened with the exploration of each business case, resulting in flexible, scalable and adaptable mineral-driven value chains for novel TE devices. It is the intention of START to co-create, together with its internal consortium members as well as external parties, a commercial ecosystem along these value chains. These ecosystems will be able to address market penetration barriers and explore opportunities along the many steps of a thermoelectrics-based value and supply chain due to the increased value in partnerships.

Creation of new market opportunities is then at the core of the work presented in this deliverable, with the exemplification of two concrete cases (Chapters 3). Due to commercialisation targets, data presented in these chapters, which showcase two different value and supply chains, is limited and restricted in order to protect the involved parties in the successful implementation and commercialisation of these chains.

2.3.1 The general START Value chain

A general approach to a TE-based value chain framework, to support START's exploitation planning activities, was already presented in Deliverable 7.1 (Report on the Foresight exercise). The general START value chain approach encompasses both Primary and Support activities, and it is the basis for drafting application-specific value and supply chains such as those presented in the following chapter.

Figure 1 presents an updated version of the general value chain with adjustments based on recent input gained from partners. Primary and Support activities represent the first layer of value chain mapping and are backed with both internal (START project) and external partners (other stakeholders). External partners are deemed necessary to cover gaps in the value chain not covered by the START partners, as well as for parts of the value chain that are to be altered for different applications.

Figure 1: START Value Chain – general.

START Primary activities

The primary activities of the START Value Chain include activities and sub-activities divided between Inbound Logistics, Operations, Outbound Logistics, Marketing & Sales, and Services. These activities range from the supply of raw materials, TEG production and system use, up to waste management and recycling.

Inbound Logistics

The phase of Inbound logistics includes the receiving, storage, and inventory control of the raw materials necessary to create the TEGs, including all relationships with the relevant suppliers. In the case of START the value chain steps covered in this phase correspond to the raw materials sourcing for p and n-type thermoelements, and the pellet material processing.

- **Raw materials sourcing (mine waste – p-type tetrahedrite):** In line with the START project objectives, raw materials sourcing encompasses the utilization of mine waste containing tetrahedrites. This ensures sustainability and repurposing of discarded resources to contribute to circularity thus minimizing environmental impact and EU's dependency on sources available outside of its territories. This will be done to the extent possible to the amount and quality of available mine waste.
- **Other materials sourcing (n-type, conditioners):** n-type thermoelements are necessary to complement the p-type tetrahedrites. These will not be obtained from waste minerals, but to be procured from other sources. Conditioners may also be needed for reaching optimal performance of p-type thermoelements.
- **TE material processing:** Refining tetrahedrite ore into high-performance TE materials demands well-defined and well-executed synthesis, processing, and production techniques, ensuring optimal material properties for efficient integration into thermoelectric devices that are suitable for

applications with different requirements (i.e., low, mid or high temperature environments). This step includes the production of both p- and n-type mineral powders by the use of High Energy Ball Milling.

Operations

The Operations phase includes the activities that convert raw materials into the finished products – the tetrahedrite-based TEGs and their integration into systems. This phase includes transforming all inputs into outputs. Activities for this phase include TEG production (including pellet and module production), TEGs' integration into a system, testing and packaging.

- **Raw pellet production:** SPS is a sintering technique used to transform the powder materials obtained through the Inbound Logistics steps by the application of pulsed direct current and axial pressure to achieve compact sheets of p-type and n-type materials, resulting in the first iteration of the future TE modules.
- **Final pellet production:** Manufacturing TE components involves precision cutting of pellets and optimizing their configuration for maximum efficiency via different mechanical steps that may include casting, grinding, polishing, metallization and sputtering. Square pellets are cut with defined proportions, ideal for the creation of application-specific TE modules.
- **TE Module production:** By using the p- and n-type pellets it is possible to create the TE modules through assembly of the pellets with other components (e.g. soldering paste, ceramic plates, etc).
- **TEG assembly:** Depending on the system requirements of an application, a TE module is applied and considered as a generator itself consisting of one module, or several modules are assembled into blocks resulting in a TEG, ready to operate. Depending on the final application, this step may include the assembly of the TEG with mounting auxiliaries, such as a heat exchanger and control system.
- **Application-specific system integration & testing:** Tailoring TE systems to specific applications requires careful planning and execution of integration and installation processes to ensure seamless and durable operation and optimal performance in the relevant environments, meeting well-known user requirements at competitive costs.
- **Packaging:** Integrated TEG systems need to be packaged and made ready to be securely shipped avoiding any potential damage that may occur during transportation.

Outbound logistics

The phase of Outbound Logistics entails all activities to distribute the final product to the end-user. This includes delivery of the product but also includes storage and distribution systems and can be external or internal. Sub-steps in this phase are order processing, storage, warehousing, transportation, distribution, delivery, on-site installation and, finally, customer support.

- **Order processing:** This step begins when a customer places an order for the integrated TEG system and involves the administrative tasks of verifying payment, updating inventory levels, and ensuring the order details are correct.
- **Storage & warehousing:** On the one hand, storage refers to the small-scale storing of products in small spaces (e.g. stocking of the integrated TEG system). On the other hand, warehousing corresponds to the practice of keeping goods in larger areas known as warehouses, for longer periods of time.
- **Transportation, Distribution, Delivery:** Distribution networks need to be designed ensuring timely delivery of the thermoelectric-based systems to the end-users. Transportation and storage

processes shall be designed to guarantee minimized delays and optimized inventory management.

- **On-site installation:** On-site Installation refers to the step where the TEG-mounted system is physically set up at the end-user's location. Installation of the system also considers user training for proper use of the device.
- **Customer Support:** This step considers guidance and support services that are crucial to assist the end-users in understanding and utilizing thermoelectric-based solutions effectively, enhancing overall satisfaction, fostering long-term relationships, while also being sources of feedback as input to the optimization of other activities such as technology development, marketing and sales.

Marketing and Sales

This phase considers the strategies to enhance visibility and target appropriate end-users' activities that help convince a consumer to purchase a TEG-based system to generate electricity from a heat difference. This phase includes the sub-steps of market analysis, development of a Marketing Strategy, advertising, customer engagement, sales and after-sales.

- **Market analysis:** The goal of the market analysis is to determine the attractiveness of the market, both now and in the future, focused on the end-use of TE devices and systems. This step can be concluded in different manners, but a common way to create a market analysis is by implementing a SWOT analysis focused on Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats that the market offers.
- **Marketing Strategy Development:** A marketing strategy refers to a business's overall plan to convince customers to buy its products or services. For TEG-based systems, the marketing strategy aims to determine how to reach prospective end-users and turn them into customers. The strategy should contain the value proposition, key brand messaging, data on target customer demographics, and other high-level elements.
- **Advertisement & Promotion:** On one hand, advertising is known to be an impersonal promotion that is typically used to draw the attention of customers towards products through a selection of paid media such as ads on different social media channels, television or newspapers. On the other hand, the step of promotion is a set of activities with the main aim of persuading the end-user to buy the TEG-based system through highlighting its advantages.
- **Sales:** The step of sales corresponds to all the activities related to selling or the number of goods sold in a given time period.
- **Customer Engagement:** Customer engagement is the process of delivering connected experiences to end-users instead of single, one-off, or fleeting transactions. It can be seen as optimizing team structure, operations, and technology to create a connected feedback loop with end-users.
- **After-Sales:** A company's after-sales service is all the help and information that it provides to customers after they have bought their product.

Services

This final phase of the Primary activities includes tasks necessary to maintain products and enhance consumer experience through customer service, maintenance, repair, refund, and exchange. It also considers waste management and recycling of the TEG products, which are very unique in their recycling approach.

- **Maintenance:** The step of product maintenance means any maintenance and support of any hardware, software, documentation, accessories, cabling, material, supplies, parts, or other goods that are part of the TEG system. Maintenance services shall ensure the continued optimal performance of tetrahedrite-based TE devices. This includes regular inspections, troubleshooting, and repairs to address any issues promptly, minimizing downtime and maximizing efficiency.
- **Waste management & recycling methodology:** Services with focus on minimizing environmental impact by implementing efficient waste management practices and recycling methods. This involves responsibly handling discarded materials, recycling components where possible, and adhering to sustainable practices to reduce waste generation throughout the product lifecycle. Concerning recycling, the steps needed to recycle TEGs might be a complicated process, furthermore once these are integrated into systems. If TEGs are to follow other recycling examples (such as batteries) they will require a controlled environment and other complex stages.
- In the case of START, this aspect is crucial to be well-addressed. Lifecycle analysis (LCA) and Life Cycle Cost (LCC) offer another layer of consideration that needs to be given to the START value chain of TE devices. As such, a structured LCA & LCC needs to be performed for each value chain case (for START this aspect is covered in Task 5.3).
- A “TEGs passport” could be also developed. Such a passport could be related to all the components, and also with the associated CO₂ emission along all the life cycle stages of the TEGs.

The START Support activities include Firm Infrastructure, Human Resource Management, Technology Development and Procurements. These have not been altered, therefore, information on these steps can be consulted in D7.1 (Report on the Foresight exercise).

START Scalability tool

An important aspect of commercialization is the scalability of the START approach and value chain, presented in Figure 2. The schematic representation serves as a tool to be used once TEG production reaches the stage when planning for upscaling becomes relevant for further developing the business. It may also be reviewed by technology developers and commercial teams at every relevant, crucial stage reached during technology development to keep scalability aspects in focus. Its elements are to be considered during decision-making, aiding products and technologies arising from the START project and ecosystem to become viable and cost-competitive for the future and for fulfilling project objectives to the maximum extent possible.

Successful scale-up may require the planning and adjustment of all activities including primary and supporting activities and along each sub-activity, which is highly dependent on the final application. Such exercise may be performed at a later stage of the START project or beyond the project duration, already during commercialization of products or services deriving from the project results by foreground owners.

Figure 2: Scalability tool for the START Value Chain.

2.3.2 The general START Supply chain

To complement the value chain, this chapter now presents a general supply chain for the development and commercialisation of tetrahedrite-based TEGs incorporated into systems for energy generation (Figure 3). The supply chain is intimately linked with the value chain steps for primary activities and focuses on the network of innovative organizations and companies that are involved in sourcing materials, creating the products and delivering the systems to the end-users.

Figure 3: START Supply chain – general.

Supply chain for Inbound logistics

This part of the supply chain focuses on the different suppliers that are needed to guarantee the sourcing of the raw materials for p- and n-type thermoelements.

- **Raw materials - mine waste for p-type tetrahedrite:** The supply of p-type tetrahedrite will be primarily coming from mine waste materials associated to copper mines, where tetrahedrites are discarded. Within the START framework several mine sites were examined in Slovakia, Austria, Portugal, Spain and Germany. At present, Slovakian sources are favoured due to the quality of tetrahedrite. Besides these sites, there are other potential targets in Europe that need to be identified and studied. The supplier of the material in this case is the mining company or the entity overseeing the mine (e.g., state-owned body).
- **Commercial raw materials for n-type and other conditioners for p-type:** Raw materials need to be acquired for n-type thermoelements, complementing the p-type ones (based on tetrahedrite). Depending on the type of n-type material desired, suppliers of metals such as Sb, Mg and Bi will need to be part of the supply chain and corresponding companies will need to be engaged. In cases where the tetrahedrite material from waste minerals does not have good properties, there is a need to acquire conditioners for p-type thermoelements, such as Fe or S, and a specific chemical supplier (or suppliers) will be needed in this step.
- **Supplier of Argon gas:** Argon gas is necessary for powder material generation. Therefore, a supplier for this type of gas is needed.
- **Supplier of containers and balls for HEBM:** The process of HEBM, necessary for the synthesis of p- and n-type powders, needs a supplier of containers and balls for this process.
- **Supplier of packaging materials:** The powders for the future p- and n-type thermoelements need to be packaged correctly before being sent for the next steps of the supply chain, where TE modules, generators and systems will be created.

Supply chain for Operations

This part of the supply chain entails several main activities, each with a specific set of partners involved. Raw pellet production from powder materials needs certain supplies. Pellet metallization and production needs the involvement of a metallization sputtering service. The TE module and TEG production, depending on the final application, might require ceramic plates, electrodes, soldering paste, substrate, coating, metal components, mechanical cooling, electricity, control system and heat exchanger. Finally, the System integration, testing and packaging of the system, requires mechanical cooling, electricity, control system, heat exchanger and packaging materials.

- **Pellet production and supplies for pellet production:** The step of raw pellet production by the SPS method is a must in the value chain, transforming powders into viable material sheets. The partner responsible for this step needs supplies to achieve the sintering, obtained through different suppliers, including the need for graphite for the SPS process.
- **Fine pellet production and metallization sputtering services:** To create pellets from the SPS obtained sheets, this step requires the involvement of a company performing the cutting of the sheets into square pellets, usually the company dedicated to the creation of the TE modules and generators, but can also be the SPS user themselves. Pellets need to go through a metallization process that needs to be guaranteed by a personalized company.
- **TE module production and corresponding supplies:** The step of creating a TE module from the thermoelement pellets might require the use of soldering paste, ceramic plates and electrodes to create the module, depending on the materials and final application. Companies need to be

involved to provide these extra materials and support the creation of the modules by a central manufacturer.

- **TEG assembly and corresponding supplies:** A full thermoelectric generator assembly is done by a dedicated TE manufacturing company but requires the involvement of suppliers of different materials for the correct assembly into TEGs i.e. suppliers of substrate, coating fluid, metal components, mounting auxiliaries for TEG assembly such as mechanical cooling, electricity, control system and heat exchangers.
- **System integration, testing and packaging suppliers:** The company selling the TEG integrated system is, usually, responsible for the system integration, testing and packaging; this entity is dependent on the final application. For the system integration there is a need to involve suppliers of mounting auxiliaries such as mechanical cooling, electricity, control system, heat exchangers, and of packaging materials.

Supply chain for Outbound logistics, Supply chain for Marketing and Sales, and Supply chain for Services

This part of the supply chain is application dependent. As a general rule, the system integrator should be the partner responsible for storage and warehousing, order processing, transportation, distribution and delivery, on-site installation and customer support. Companies can be subcontracted at specific steps of these supply chains to cover some arising needs.

2.3.3 Partners and roles in the START value and supply chains

Currently there is no structured thermoelectrics value chain built around tetrahedrite-based TE devices. Therefore, what START is trying to accomplish is quite innovative and unique. The previous sub-chapters described the main value chain players and necessary suppliers along the general START value chain.

Within its consortium, START already has the relevant players covering the main steps of Inbound logistics and also covering the majority of steps within Operations. Responsibilities are well defined, aligned and are essential to keep the value chain operational in its path toward commercialization:

1. Partners with geoscience background and geo-business profiles (BGR, LNEG, IGME, GeoSphere and SGUDS) are responsible for identifying tailings, characterising minerals, issuing and delivering the selected materials to the partners involved in raw material processing.
2. Once the materials are sourced to the processing partners, it is their responsibility to ensure the continuation of inbound logistics tasks, including the first steps in material synthesis and processing. MBN and GeniCore are responsible for these steps involving the activities of TE material synthesis (HEBM) and TE material consolidation (sintering).
3. After processing, and once square pellets are produced by SPS, these materials are sent to the partners who are responsible for module and TEG assembly, which in START are represented by RGS and TEGnology. For these companies tasks include coating of thermoelectric materials, electrical bonding and final module/generators production while some activities such as soldering or sputtering are outsourced to businesses offering these services.

Wherever necessary, suppliers of different consumables (e.g. conditioning raw materials, heat exchangers, etc.) will be part of the supply chain in order to fulfill these mentioned steps. There are a number of different suppliers needed, depending on the finality of the designated working step, and not all suppliers are needed. Their involvement is also application dependent.

It is from the later stage of Operations into the following stages that the START supply chain is lacking contributors. First, the value chain/ecosystem lacks specific system integrators who can combine TE devices into existing systems (e.g. coupling a TE device into a biomass burner). This aspect of integration includes the design of the overall system, and it is highly application-dependent, contrasting with the previous value chain steps. Secondly, there is a need to create systematic Outbound logistics represented by distribution, logistics, guidance, and support for the operation of the coupled TEG-system. System integrators should be able to contribute to these steps, as well as in the realm of Marketing and Sales. Finally, system integrators should also be responsible for the maintenance of the systems and the waste management and recycling of components, whenever relevant. As a system integrator is a pivotal player of the TE value chain and overall ecosystem, emphasis on choosing a suitable partner for this role is crucial and shall be carefully planned according to the application and targeted customer segment.

3 INDUSTRIAL AND BUSINESS VIABILITY OF THE START APPROACH

The present chapter, building on the general value chain and supply chain framework, introduces the progress made in developing models and tools to assess START-based applications' industrial and economic viability. It also addresses the business plan development of two different applications built on the START value chain, covering the set-up of relevant supply chains as well as their industrial and economic feasibility aspects.

3.1 MODELS AND TOOLS FOR VIABILITY ASSESSMENT

Through studying potential TEG-based applications generated by the START project, models and tools have been developed that can be used to plan further applications based on TEG-based applications using tetrahedrites as key raw material. These tools enable the thorough review of microeconomic feasibility aspects, extended also to conventional materials and technologies and can provide substantial support via techno-economic analysis at all major production stages. The START tools may effectively be used for decision-making on launching businesses and investing in the commercialization of TEG-based applications.

3.1.1 START TEG-based System CAPEX Modelling

The "START TEG-based System CAPEX Modelling" tool (Figure 4) presents a method for estimating the capital expenditure (CAPEX) required to produce and implement TEG-based systems. Designed in line with the START value and supply chains, it enables performing a thorough break-down of costs associated with complex production processes into understandable and measurable components, empowering stakeholders with a clear understanding of the financial and technical considerations involved in TEG-based applications. By focusing on key items of materials and labour costs associated with the production stages from raw material processing to system integration, this modelling framework addresses the challenges and opportunities associated with deploying the START technology for a wide range of potential applications.

The tool was designed with a modular and adaptable structure. Users can input parameters specific to their application — such as a biomass furnace boiler or solar photovoltaic (PV) system — ensuring the results are tailored to the unique demands of each use case. This flexibility extends to other variables as well, such as the number of TEG modules, pellet composition, and material costs, making the model applicable across several application scenarios. Key Performance Indicators include the most important metrics such as cost per watt and payback period calculated based on system sizing and performance targeting, supporting strategic planning for scaling up production and planning larger installations or multiple system deployments. The "START TEG-based System CAPEX Modelling" tool can be further refined and can potentially become relevant for industries with large waste heat output.

START TEG-BASED SYSTEM CAPEX modelling

System = Application for energy generation mounted with thermoelectric generators (TEGs) for electricity generation & enhanced efficiency via capturing waste heat.
 Application examples: biomass furnace boiler, solar PV system. TEG = includes 1 or more TE modules.
 TE module = includes certain amount of pellets for a p-type leg and same amount of pellets for an n-type leg.
 Pellet = include 1 leg of p-type and 1 leg of n-type elements. Prepared from SPS sintered disks of p-type and n-type thermoelectric elements (metal powder).

Process Steps	Unit	Ideal market entry situation	Future running commercial situation	Explanation
System production volume/year	[pieces]	50	300	Target number of systems (applications) produced per year.
PELLET SPECIFICATIONS AND RAW MATERIAL COSTS				
<i>To be filled in with figures based on application specifications</i>				
Pellet dimensions	[mm3]	x*y*z	x*y*z	Dimensions specified as length*width*height.
Size of a module	[mm2*mm2]	x*y	x*y	Area to be covered by 1 module.
Area of a module	[mm2]			
Density	[kg/dm3]			Assumed equal both for p and n-type. Example, to be adjusted.
Pellets per module	[pieces]			Scenario example: 40 p-type + 40 n-type
Weight	[g/module]			The approximate weight of 1 module. Example, to be adjusted.
Costs: Minerals	[EUR/kg]			Costs based on price obtained from mines offering tetrahedrites
Amount of Mineral in p-type	[g]	0	0	Formula
Cost of elements in p-type (Cu, Sb, S, Zn...)	[EUR/module]	0	0	p-type tetrahedrite: Zinc antimonide - decreased costs in case of continuous collaboration
Cost of elements in n-type (Mg, Sb, Bi, V)	[EUR/module]			n-type: Mg3.35Sb1.5Bi0.5 (V doped) (to be adjusted based on application need)
Total cost of raw materials per module	[EUR/module]	0	0	Total cost of raw materials per module including p-type and n-type elements
LABOUR COSTS FOR MATERIAL SYNTHESIS, POWDER PROCESSING & PRODUCTION; RAW PELLET and FINE PELLET PRODUCTION				
Labour costs				
Material synthesis & powder production	[EUR/module]			Estimation, to be adjusted based on the application requirements (MBN)
SPS Sintering /DISK production	[EUR/module]			Estimation, to be adjusted based on the application requirements (GENICORE)
Pellet Casting, Dicing, Polishing	[EUR/module]			Estimation, to be adjusted by pellet manufacturer (RGS/TEGology)/ supplier (grinding and cutting services)
Metallization	[EUR/module]			Estimation, to be adjusted by pellet manufacturer (RGS/TEGology)/ supplier (sputtering services)
Any other labour costs?	[EUR/module]			
Total:	[EUR/module]	0	0	
ADDITIONAL MATERIALS FOR MATERIAL SYNTHESIS, POWDER PROCESSING & PRODUCTION; RAW PELLET and FINE PELLET PRODUCTION				
Material supplies not covered under 'Pellet Materials'				
Argon gas	[EUR/module]			Material costs occurring during material synthesis & powder production (MBN) incl. packaging materials & shipment fee
Graphite	[EUR/module]			Graphite material for sintering tooling sets (GENICORE) incl. packaging materials & shipment fee
Pellet Casting, Dicing, Polishing	[EUR/module]			If relevant. Occurred by the Pellet producer (RGS/TEGology) or by its supplier i.e. grinding and cutting services (TBO)
Any other material?	[EUR/module]			
Total:	[EUR/module]	0	0	
LABOUR COSTS FOR MODULE PRODUCTION				
Labour costs occurring during module production				
TE Module production	[EUR/module]			Module producers' labour costs on producing the TE module (in case a 1 TE module = TEG, it involves the TEG assembly, too)
Tops & bottoms processing	[EUR/module]			Module producers' labour costs on producing the TE module (if relevant) i.e. Bonding
Any other labour costs?	[EUR/module]			
Total:	[EUR/module]	0	0	
MATERIALS FOR MODULE PRODUCTION				
Material supplies occurring during module production				
Top & Bottom Materials	[EUR/module]			Material costs occurred by the module producer (i.e. Ceramic plates & electrodes OR substrate, etc.)
Soldering pastes	[EUR/module]			Module producers' material costs - soldering/silver paste
Service costs, if any	[EUR/module]			Service costs of activities outsourced to external provider by the module producer, if any
Any other materials/services?	[EUR/module]			
Total:	[EUR/module]	0	0	
Labour TEG ASSEMBLY				
Relevant if TEG is built from several modules				
Coating process	[EUR/module]			TEG producers' labour costs
Bonding/Plating/Brazing process	[EUR/module]			
Bonding & soldering hot side	[EUR/module]			
Bonding & soldering cold side	[EUR/module]			
TEG Mounting process	[EUR/module]			
Any other process costs?	[EUR/module]			
Total:	[EUR/module]	0	0	
Materials TEG ASSEMBLY				
Relevant if TEG is built from several modules				
Coating fluid	[EUR/module]			TEG producers' material costs for coating
Heat exchanger	[EUR/module]			if relevant for the application
Heat sink	[EUR/module]			if relevant for the application
Metal components	[EUR/module]			Components of general machinery
Mounting auxiliaries for TEG assembly	[EUR/module]			Assembly costs of several modules into a TEG (i.e. Mechanical cooling, electricity, control system, heat exchanger)
Any other material?	[EUR/module]			
Total:	[EUR/module]	0	0	
TOTAL COSTS - TEG production				
Cost-efficiency indicators for planning/monitoring				
Total Labour Costs (Processing)	[EUR/module]	0	0	
Total Materials Costs	[EUR/module]	0	0	
Total Costs Per TEG/module	[EUR/module]	0	0	
Labour SYSTEM INTEGRATION & TESTING & PACKAGING				
Application specific cost items				
Labour cost of system integration	[EUR/system]			labour costs occurring by the system integrator (i.e. Biomass furnace builder or solar panel manufacturer)
Labour cost of system testing	[EUR/system]			labour costs occurring by the system integrator (i.e. Biomass furnace builder or solar panel manufacturer)
Labour cost of packaging	[EUR/system]			labour costs occurring by the system integrator (i.e. Biomass furnace builder or solar panel manufacturer)
Total:	[EUR/system]	0	0	
Materials SYSTEM INTEGRATION & TESTING & PACKAGING				
System: TEG-mounted application				
Base application	[EUR/system]			i.e. TEG-mounted biomass boiler, TEG-mounted solar pv panel
Auxiliaries: mechanical cooling	[EUR/system]			considering application specifications
Auxiliaries: electricity	[EUR/system]			wiring needed for system integration
Auxiliaries: control system	[EUR/system]			considering application specifications
Auxiliaries: heat sink	[EUR/system]			aluminium heat sink produced by extrusion
Auxiliaries: heat exchanger	[EUR/system]			typical heat exchanger meeting application specification needs
Packaging materials	[EUR/system]			ensuring safe storage and delivery after successful system testing
Total:	[EUR/system]	0	0	
TOTAL SYSTEM COSTS - TEG-MOUNTED APPLICATION				
per system, specific for the application (i.e. total number of modules per 1 solar panel/ biomass furnace)				
Modules per System	[pieces]			
Total Labour Costs	[EUR/system]	0	0	
Total Materials Costs	[EUR/system]	0	0	
Total System Costs	[EUR/system]	0	0	TEG-mounted application costs (i.e. of 1 TEG-mounted solar panel/ costs of 1 TEG-mounted biomass furnace)
Per m2	[EUR/m2]	0	0	
Per W	[EUR/W]	0.00	0.00	based on 4500 W/m2 system
Per W size of Flex-TEG-Solart System	[EUR/W]	0.0	0.0	in case of 0.5kW system
KPIs for TEG production & Application-specific System production				
Key performance indicators for cost-efficiency planning/monitoring				
Total Cost of Raw Materials per System	[EUR/system]	0	0	per system, specific for the application
Total System Costs per m2	[EUR/m2]	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	application specific indicator
Power target	[W]			0 power targeted
Performance target /system	[W/m2]			0 system sizing - i.e. Performance capacity of a CHP system
Total costs of performance per W	[EUR/W]	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	
Any other indicators?				

Figure 4: START TEG-based System CAPEX Modelling Tool.

3.1.2 START Benchmarking and Competition Assessment

Another modelling approach developed in the START project framework is the START TEG-Based System Benchmarking and Competition tool that further supports the rapid modelling of technical and economic feasibility of product concepts built on START TEGs (Figure 5). It is an Excel-based platform that helps users compare their START TEG-based solutions with reference benchmarks and existing market alternatives, providing valuable insights for developers, investors, and energy analysts.

The structure of the tool is centred on a comparative table that organizes key data points for benchmarking. Users can insert introductory information of practical applicability as well as key data for consideration. The table includes a standard reference application such as a conventional solution and three (or more) competing solutions. These may be innovative, commercially available distinct technologies, or other systems designed for waste heat recovery and energy efficiency, as well as widely adopted solutions representing current market standards. This framework allows for an in-depth evaluation of how TEG-based systems measure up against various alternatives.

START TEG-BASED SYSTEM Benchmarking & Competition

Table gathers the major system specifications and parameters that may support benchmarking and in-depth analysis of competitors. Data of START TEG-based systems developed for different applications may be compared to a case used for benchmarking and to main competing applications available on the market.

Specifications & Parameters	Unit	Benchmarking case	START TEG-based System	Competitor no.1: Comparable innovative solution (commercially available)	Competitor no. 2: Comparable innovative solution (commercially available)	Competitor no. 3: Commonly applied solution (widely commercialized)
System introduction: Solution for electricity & heat provision		Use case based on solutions used by the targeted customers	Introduction of START TEG based system for waste heat recovery & enhanced energy efficiency	Introduction of solution - Competitor no.1	Introduction of solution - Competitor no.2	Introduction of solution - Competitor no.3
Fuel Type	n.a.	ie. gas + grid electricity	ie. biomass, TE	ie. biomass , helium	ie. gas	biomass, batteries, oil
Operating Temperature Range	°C					
Electricity storage need (battery max. usable storage capacity)	kWh					
Inverter need						
Required additional components						
Electrical Output	kW					
Thermal Output	kW					
Overall Efficiency	%					
Size of the system	m²					
Weight	kg					
Noise Level (dB)	dB					
Emissions (CO2, NOx levels)	g/kWh					
Heat Storage Capacity	liters					
Required Maintenance Frequency	years					
Initial Purchase Cost (including shipment?)	€					
Installation Cost	€					
System CAPEX (Cost of Purchase + Installation)	€	0	0	0	0	
Maintenance Cost per Year	€					
Fuel need per year (pellet or gas)	kg or kW					
Fuel price (1kg pellet or 1kW gas)	€					
Fuel Cost per Year	€	0	0	0	0	0
Electricity need per year	kWh					
Thermal energy need per year	kWh					
Insurance,Taxes,Other recurring expenses/ year	€					
Expected Lifespan	years					
System OPEX (Cost of fuel+maintenance+any other)/year	€	0	0	0	0	
End-of-life Disposal costs	€					
Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) over the entire lifespan <small>(capex+opex+replacement+upgrade+eol)*lifespan: the full financial commitment required for owning and operating the system</small>	€	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Hours of operation (per year)	hours					
Electrical energy produced (yearly)	kWh		0.00	0.00	0.00	
Electricity tariffs per kWh	€	0.29	0.29	0.29	0.29	
Electricity benefits (savings)/year	€	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Thermal energy produced (yearly)	kWh		0.00	0.00	0.00	
Thermal energy tariffs per kWh (gas price)	€	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	
Thermal energy benefits/ year	€	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Available Subsidies or Incentives/ year	€					
Total financial benefits per year	€	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Total financial benefits per total lifespan	€	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Return on Investment (ROI) in 10 years =gross profit of investment - amount invested/amount invested *100	%	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
Payback Period (time of investment fully returned) = total costs invested/benefit obtained over a year	years	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!

Figure 5: START Benchmarking and Competition Assessment Tool.

Key specifications, financial and operational metrics are highlighted in the tool that may be adjusted according to the application in focus. Main metrics include the system's capital expenditures, which represent the initial purchase and installation costs, and operational expenditures (OPEX), which cover annual maintenance and fuel expenses. The tool also calculates the total cost of ownership (TCO), incorporating CAPEX, OPEX, upgrades, and end-of-life costs over the system's overall lifespan. Other essential metrics include annual and lifetime financial benefits, return on investment (ROI), and the

payback period required to recover initial costs. These metrics give a clear picture of the economic viability of TEG-based solutions.

By comparing systems based on these specifications, the tool supports rapid and informed decision-making. It highlights the potential advantages of tetrahedrite-based TEGs, which are designed to offer lower costs, flexible scalability, and enhanced sustainability compared to competing technologies. This analysis enables stakeholders to identify opportunities for market competitiveness and optimize their energy solutions. The benchmarking tool is not just a modelling aid; it serves as a strategic asset for evaluating renewable energy systems. Its ability to assess costs and benefits comprehensively ensures that TEG-based systems can be positioned effectively as innovative, cost-efficient, and eco-friendly alternatives in the renewable energy market. By simplifying complex evaluations, it reinforces the role of TEG-based technologies in addressing the growing need for sustainable energy solutions.

START tools have been tested and tuned based on selected showcases of potential commercial applications that are introduced in the following section of the report. Modelling will be adjusted with the involvement of industrial and research partners based on outcomes of work packages running parallel as well as on up-to-date data on the present TRL of thermoelectrics and on the relevant business environment including existing markets where TEGs may become potential players.

3.2 APPLICATIONS BUILT ON THE START VALUE CHAIN

Different paths of the START value chain for mid temperature waste heat recovery with two specific applications are under development, led by two key industrial project partners having TEG developer business background. These value chains are similar at their core, but they present some differences such as pellet material composition, pellet and TEG sizing and design, solutions for system integration and further commercialization steps customized for the applications and for the targeted end-users.

The Lean Canvas Model¹⁸ was used to study their business ideas and opportunities. Dedicated subchapters summarize the main outcomes for both applications. The information may be further used for drafting business plan outlines and detailed plans in case assumptions and calculations confirm technical and commercial feasibilities of these use cases.

3.2.1 Medium temperature TE value chain - TE & Biomass (RGS)

Business case - START μ CHP-TEG System: Market potential and future vision of Micro-Combined Heat and Power System on biomass mounted with TEG for enhanced energy efficiency

The START μ CHP-TEG System is designed and has been developed by RGS Development B.V., one of the leading TEG developing companies of the START consortium. The driving force for the development of such an application was the intention to create a relatively simple and unique system for waste heat recovery, not yet available on the market. Techno-economic aspects studied so far show promising potential for a near-future successful market entry at relatively low investment needs with this pellet furnace based micro-combined heat and power system mounted with RGS's thermoelectric generator. The system offers green energy with minimal dependency through one system capable of solving all energy needs across the year combined with solar or wind and battery systems, if necessary.

The market potential for a μ CHP-TEG system based on recent market reports is substantial, driven by a growing demand for sustainable energy solutions. Globally, the micro-CHP market is projected to grow

¹⁸ <https://www.leanfoundry.com/tools/lean-canvas>

significantly, with estimates of certain sources suggesting that the value at 3.1 billion in 2024 will reach a market value of \$4.8 billion by 2029, expanding at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9.4% during the forecast period¹⁹.

Figure 6: Market potential of μ CHP systems.

Asia-Pacific and Europe dominate the market due to their strong policies on sustainability and energy efficiency. The residential and small commercial sectors have emerged as the primary adopters of micro-CHP systems, thanks to their dual benefits of heat and electricity generation at high efficiencies²⁰.

The market potential for micro combined heat and power (μ CHP) systems in Europe, particularly for biomass-powered variants with integrated thermoelectric generators, is significant and growing, especially in rural and remote areas. Europe has a strong emphasis on decentralized energy solutions, making μ CHP systems an attractive option for addressing energy needs in areas with limited access to centralized electricity grids. Biomass-based μ CHP systems are especially compelling as they leverage locally available resources, reducing transportation costs and ensuring energy independence for rural communities²¹.

In 2013, the μ CHP market in Europe was estimated with an annual potential of approximately one million units. These systems are particularly well-suited for residential and small commercial applications, offering both heat and electricity generation from a single energy source. Germany, the Netherlands, and the UK are leading the adoption of μ CHP technologies, but there is significant untapped potential in remote regions across other European countries. Biomass-powered μ CHP systems integrated with TEGs hold unique advantages, such as enhanced efficiency and the ability to recover waste heat for electricity generation. This is particularly beneficial for communities that rely on biomass for heating, as it enables dual-purpose energy use while reducing carbon emissions. With supportive EU policies focused on sustainability, competitiveness, and energy security, the adoption of biomass μ CHP-TEG systems is likely to expand, driven by increasing energy costs, the need for emission reductions, and the transition to renewable energy sources²².

Future growth in this sector is expected to be driven by innovations in TEG technology, further reducing costs and improving system efficiencies. Additionally, rural and remote areas in Europe represent a promising market segment due to their reliance on decentralized energy systems, particularly in regions where the infrastructure for natural gas or other centralized energy sources is underdeveloped. These

¹⁹ <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/micro-chp-market-419.html>

²⁰ <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/industry-reports/micro-combined-heat-and-power-market-100143>

²¹ eranetbioenergy.net

²² [Build Up](#)

µCHP-TEG systems can play a critical role in achieving Europe’s renewable energy and carbon neutrality goals while offering practical energy solutions for underserved areas. Figures highlight the strong commercial potential of biomass µCHP-TEG systems, particularly in Europe, where rural and remote energy needs, combined with favorable policies, create a promising market landscape. As technology adoption scales and costs reduce, these systems can capture larger shares of their respective total available, serviceable available and obtainable market (TAM, SAM, SOM). TAM may be calculated based on the number of homes and residential buildings with average need for 0.5-1 kW system capacities, SAM may be assessed based on such homes located in rural areas of Europe, while SOM may be calculated based on homes with pellet boilers. These market indicators are to be further adjusted and studied along the business plan development of the refined START µCHP-TEG application and business focus²³.

Business case - START µCHP-TEG System: Lean Canvas - START µCHP-TEG System

Necessary elements from the market uptake strategy have been gathered and modelled on a Lean Canvas. This is a one-page business plan template adapted from the Business Canvas Model for start-ups and innovators of new ideas²⁴. It helps deconstruct a business idea using twelve business modelling building blocks of key assumptions. The model is designed to help quick decision-making along business development with a customer-centric approach that, in the longer run, may encourage new players to join the business ecosystem created by the START project. The main blocks for RGS’s START-based application are shown below (Figure 7 and text thereafter).

Lean Canvas– µCHP-TEG System <small>Micro-Combined Heat and Power System on biomass mounted with TEG for enhanced energy efficiency</small>				
Problem	Solution	Unique Value Proposition	Unfair Advantage	Customer Segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Across year green electricity generation is challenging at rural areas • Existing solutions for energy independency are costly, not sufficiently green and not well optimised for fluctuating energy needs around the year • The need for self-sufficient green energy supply is not well addressed by the market 	The START µCHP system of TEG-mounted biomass furnace is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green, sustainable and capable of providing continuous heat & electricity complementary to solar, wind and batteries • Low maintenance required (reliable, durable, stable) • Modular assembly enables enhanced recyclability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green energy with minimal dependency through one system capable of solving all energy needs, likely to be combined with solar or wind and with a battery system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplified TEG integration approach providing unique opportunity for upgrading pellet furnaces • Patented system • LCA and LCC results confirm increased environmental and financial sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residential Users: Homeowners and small residential communities • Commercial Users: SMEs, including restaurants, hotels, and retail outlets • Industrial Users: Small manufacturing plants and agricultural facilities • Public Sector: Schools, hospitals, and government buildings
Existing Alternatives	Key Metrics	High-Level Concept	Channels	Early Adopters
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Grid based fossil solutions (gas, powerplants) 2. Grid based green solutions (solar parks, wind parks, biomass plants) 3. Locally based partially green solutions (heat from fossil, likely combined with solar and batteries) 4. Locally based green solutions (biomass furnace with Stirling engine, combined with solar and batteries) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Energy Savings for Customers 2. Payback Period 3. Maintenance Frequency and Cost 4. Customer Acquisition Cost (CAC) 5. Lead Time for Delivery 6. Revenue per Customer 7. Installation and Setup Time 8. System Performance Uptime 9. Fuel Consumption Efficiency 10. Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Independency - Green, Sustainable, Continuous, Reliable and Durable Provision of Heat & Electricity for Rural Homeowners 	Sales: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Retail Partnerships with businesses selling heat and electricity generating systems 2. Distribution Agreements - Local Distributors: - Direct Sales 3. Installer and Contractor Networks 4. Online Sales Platforms 5. Government and Municipal Programs (subsidising) Marketing: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> A. Social Media and Influencer Marketing B. Content Marketing and Educational Outreach C. Referral Programs and Customer Advocacy D. Industry Trade Shows and Exhibitions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Owners of buildings at cold/moderate climate at rural or off-the-grid locations who value both energy efficiency and sustainability • Owners of Energy-Efficient Homes: focused on maximizing energy efficiency and reducing utility costs • High-Energy-Use Households: with high energy consumption due to heating, or electricity-intensive activities • Green Builders and Developers: focused on constructing energy-efficient or zero-energy homes
Cost Structure			Revenue Structure	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product & Development Costs • Manufacturing and Logistics Costs • Sales and Marketing Expenses • Installation and Service Costs • Operational Overheads • Compliance and Regulatory Costs • Supply Chain Costs: Supplier management, inventory management, procurement • Grants and Subsidy Management • Miscellaneous Costs: Travel, employee training, etc. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct Sales Revenue: From selling Flex-TEG Solar Systems, customizations, and installation services • Recurring Revenue Streams: Maintenance contracts and subscription-based offerings • Energy Sales and Partnerships: Income from feed-in tariffs, revenue sharing with utilities, and partnerships with strategic allies • Financial Products: Leasing options, financing interest, and government subsidies • Additional Revenue: Licensing fees, research grants, and affiliate program income 	
<small>Lean Canvas is adapted from The Business Model Canvas by LeanFoundry. Word implementation by: Neos Chronos Limited (https://neoschronos.com). License: CC BY-SA 3.0</small>				

Figure 7: Lean Canvas of Business Case for the START µCHP-TEG System.

²³ [Expobiomasa](https://expobiomasa.com)

²⁴ <https://www.leanfoundry.com/tools/lean-canvas>

Problem

The first box of the Lean Canvas introduces the three main problems the solution must address. At present, the list below includes those of major concern in line with the targeted business case.

- Electricity generation is challenging in rural areas;
- Existing solutions for energy independence are costly, not sufficiently green and not well optimised for fluctuating energy needs around the year;
- The need for a self-sufficient green energy supply is not well addressed by the market.

Solution

The START μ CHP-TEG System is:

- Green, sustainable and capable of providing continuous heat & electricity;
- Requires low maintenance (reliable, durable, stable);
- Modular assembly enables enhanced recyclability.

Unique Value Proposition

The Unique Value Proposition stating why it is worth buying such a system is: *'Green energy with minimal dependency through one system capable of solving all energy needs, likely to be combined with solar or wind and with a battery system'*.

High-Level concept

Designed for capturing the attention and interest of stakeholders.

'Energy Independency - Green, Sustainable, Continuous, Reliable and Durable Provision of Heat & Electricity for Rural Homeowners'.

Unfair Advantage

Reasons why it can't be easily copied, including characteristics that competitors can't match are defined as per below:

- Simplified TEG integration approach providing unique opportunity for upgrading pellet furnaces;
- Patented system;
- LCA and LCC results confirm increased environmental and financial sustainability.

Customer Segments

Four major segments are targeted, of which the first one is in lead focus:

- **Residential Users:** Homeowners and small residential communities looking to reduce energy costs and enhance energy security;
- **Commercial Users:** SMEs, including restaurants, hotels, and retail outlets, that benefit from combined heat and power generation;
- **Industrial Users:** Small manufacturing plants and agricultural facilities that can utilize waste heat for process heating and power generation;
- **Public Sector:** Schools, hospitals, and governmental buildings aiming to reduce energy costs and environmental impact.

Early Adopters

Using the customer segments, early adopters include the most promising customers in order of importance:

- **Owners of buildings at cold/moderate climate at rural or off-the-grid locations** who value both energy efficiency and sustainability;
- **Owners of Energy-Efficient Homes:** Focused on maximizing energy efficiency and reducing utility costs; typical early adopters of new home technologies, such as smart thermostats, solar panels, or advanced insulation;
- **High-Energy-Use Households:** Larger households with high energy consumption due to heating, or other electricity-intensive activities may seek to reduce their utility bills; having the financial capability to invest in technologies offering long-term savings;
- **Green Builders and Developers:** Focused on constructing energy-efficient or zero-energy homes might integrate the START μ CHP-TEG System to enhance the appeal of their properties; typically looking to differentiate their projects in the market by offering cutting-edge sustainable technologies.

Depending on further progress of the business case development, the list of early adopters may be adjusted and extended with other potential candidates such as energy-conscious communities and cooperatives (i.e. eco-villages, cohousing communities) often organized around principles of sustainability and that may have shared energy resources or infrastructure. Furthermore, depending on country-specific devotion, national governments or NGO-funded demonstration projects may fasten up market uptake and acceptance through pilot projects showcasing the potential of the START systems in public buildings or as part of community energy initiatives.

Channels

Sales and marketing channels used by the pellet furnace builder are thought to be a mixture of the following possibilities:

Sales channels:

1. **Retail Partnerships with businesses selling heat and electricity generating systems:**
 - **Home Improvement Stores:** Partnerships with big multinational chains, or local equivalents for selling the system;
 - **Renewable Energy Retailers:** Specialized retailers of sustainable / renewable energy products.
2. **Distribution Agreements:**
 - **Local Distributors:** Use local distributors to reach markets that may not be easily accessible through direct sales or online channels;
 - **Direct Sales:** A dedicated sales team targeting homeowners, residential developers, contractors, and large-scale property managers. Direct engagement with homeowners and businesses to explain the benefits of the START μ CHP-TEG System and provide customized solutions.
3. **Installer and Contractor Networks:**
 - **Certified Installers:** Building a network of certified installers who can sell, install, and maintain the systems;

- **Partnerships with HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) Companies:** Leverage existing HVAC companies that are expanding into renewable energy solutions to offer the system as part of their product line.
- 4. **Online Sales Platform:**
 - **E-commerce Website:** With product information, online purchasing, and installation scheduling;
 - **Online Marketplaces:** Major e-commerce platforms (i.e. Amazon, Alibaba), specialized energy equipment sites.
- 5. **Government and Municipal Programs:**
 - **Inclusion in Government Subsidy Programs:** Work with government agencies to include the micro-CHP system in subsidy or rebate programs aimed at reducing carbon emissions and promoting renewable energy use;
 - **Municipal Projects:** Target municipal and public sector projects, offering the system as part of energy efficiency and sustainability initiatives.

Marketing channels:

- A. **Social Media and Influencer Marketing:**
 - **Targeted Social Media Campaigns:** Use platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram to reach early adopters and tech-savvy consumers interested in sustainable living;
 - **Influencer Partnerships:** Collaborate with influencers and bloggers in the renewable energy and home improvement sectors to promote the system.
- B. **Content Marketing and Educational Outreach:**
 - **Webinars and Online Workshops:** Hosting webinars and workshops to educate potential customers on the benefits of micro-CHP systems and how they can improve energy efficiency and reduce costs;
 - **SEO and Content Marketing:** Develop a strong online presence with SEO-optimized content, blog posts, and educational videos to attract organic traffic.
- C. **Referral Programs and Customer Advocacy:**
 - **Case Studies and Testimonials:** Use customer success stories to build credibility and attract new clients through word-of-mouth;
 - **Referral Incentives:** Offer existing customers incentives for referring new customers to the business.
- D. **Industry Trade Shows and Exhibitions:**
 - **Energy and Sustainability Expos:** Participate in trade shows and exhibitions focused on renewable energy, HVAC, and green building solutions to showcase the product;
 - **Demonstration Projects:** Set up demonstration projects in collaboration with local governments or NGOs to showcase the system in action.

Existing alternatives

The list below gathers conventional approaches as well as solutions mostly used by rural homeowners & other targeted customers while the exact mix of solutions varies depending on the region's climate, availability of resources, and the homeowner's specific needs. In the frame of the business case development, commercially available solutions are picked and compared to the START μ CHP-TEG

System use case based on main aspects that are crucial for successful market entry and durable competition.

1. **Grid based fossil solutions:** Systems relying on centralized fossil fuel power plants, such as gas turbines or coal-fired stations, which supply electricity and heat through large-scale infrastructure, but contribute significantly to greenhouse gas emissions;
2. **Grid based green solutions:** Renewable energy sources of solar parks, wind parks or biomass plants providing sustainable energy to the grid, reducing carbon footprints while addressing the variability of natural resources;
3. **Locally based partially green solutions:** Hybrid systems integrating fossil-fuel-based heating with renewable elements like solar panels and battery storage, aiming to improve sustainability without completely eliminating reliance on fossil fuels;
4. **Locally based green solutions:** Fully renewable setups using biomass for heating, often paired with a Stirling engine to generate electricity, supported by solar power and batteries for energy storage to maximize efficiency and minimize environmental impact.

Key metrics

Key Performance Indicators of business success & viability monitoring have been reviewed along and the main potential metrics have been identified and are listed in order of importance with respect to the present development stage.

1. **Energy Savings for Customers:** The average energy cost savings that customers experience after installing the START μ CHP-TEG System. This is a key selling point and customer satisfaction metric;
2. **Payback Period:** Time to recover investment through energy savings for customers;
3. **Maintenance Frequency and Cost:** The average frequency and cost of maintenance visits. Lower maintenance requirements can be a key selling point and improve long-term profitability;
4. **Customer Acquisition Cost (CAC):** The average cost incurred to acquire a new customer, including marketing, sales, and installation costs;
5. **Lead Time for Delivery:** The average time from order placement to delivery and installation of the START μ CHP-TEG System. Shorter lead times improve customer experience;
6. **Revenue per Customer:** The average revenue generated from each customer, including initial purchase, installation, and ongoing maintenance sales;
7. **Installation and Setup Time:** The average time required to complete the installation and setup of the system at a customer's home. This impacts customer satisfaction and operational efficiency;
8. **System Performance Uptime:** The percentage of time the μ CHP system is operational and producing energy without interruptions. High uptime is crucial for customer satisfaction;
9. **Fuel Consumption Efficiency:** The amount of biomass fuel required to generate a specific amount of electricity and heat. This metric is important for cost-effectiveness and sustainability;
10. **Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT):** A measure of how satisfied customers are with the product, installation process, and after-sales service, typically collected through surveys.

Cost structure

Key costs associated with operating the business.

- **Product and Development Costs:** These expenses cover the research and development needed to optimize TEG performance, integrate components into a cohesive system, and design custom solutions tailored to specific applications;
- **Manufacturing and Logistics Costs** (component costs, labour, shipping, warehousing): This category includes the cost of raw materials, labour for assembly, transportation of finished products, and storage prior to distribution;
- **Sales and Marketing Expenses** (advertising, commissions, trade shows, promotional materials): These are the costs associated with promoting the product, including ad campaigns, sales team incentives, event participation, and producing marketing collateral;
- **Installation and Service Costs:** These are covering the expenses of deploying the product at customer sites, providing ongoing support, and honouring warranty obligations;
- **Operational Overheads:** General business costs like office space rental, IT technology and infrastructure, fees of legal services, and administrative functions fall under this category;
- **Compliance and Regulatory Costs:** These expenses ensure the product meets industry standards and regulatory requirements, including obtaining certifications and handling legal documentation such as permits and licenses;
- **Supply Chain Costs:** Includes costs related to sourcing components, managing supplier relationships, procurement and inventory levels for smooth production operations;
- **Grants and Subsidy Management:** These include the effort on grant application and management including secure financial assistance and compliance with the reporting requirements of funding agencies;
- **Miscellaneous Costs:** Additional expenses such as business travel for meetings, trade events, training programs to upskill employees and any other costs not included in the above categories are reviewed and accounted for here.

Revenue structure

Streams of income; both recurring and upfront revenue opportunities are listed below.

- **Direct Sales Revenue:** Obtained from selling START μ CHP-TEG Systems, customizations, and installation services. This represents the core income generated through the sale of main products and related services, including customized configurations and professional installation to meet diverse customer needs;
- **Recurring Revenue Streams:** Maintenance contracts, monitoring services, fuel sales, and subscription-based offerings. These ongoing income sources shall provide predictable cash flow, supported by long-term customer relationships through maintenance agreements and subscription plans for performance monitoring;
- **Energy Sales and Partnerships:** Income from feed-in tariffs, revenue sharing with utilities, and partnerships with strategic allies. Revenue from exporting excess electricity to the grid, sharing profits with utility providers, and collaborating with industry partners strengthens the business's financial model and sustainability;
- **Financial Products:** Leasing options, financing interest, and government subsidies. Income deriving from offering flexible financial plans, such as leases or loans, is often enhanced by government support programs and tax incentives encouraging the adoption of the innovation;
- **Additional Revenue:** Licensing fees, research grants, and affiliate program income. These supplementary streams include earning from intellectual property rights, funding for innovation and research, and commissions from affiliate partnerships that expand market reach.

With the knowledge gathered above the business case of the START μ CHP-TEG System has been further developed with focus on modelling the capital expenditures of the application as well as looking into operational expenditures along benchmarking and competitors' analysis using the tools created in the frame of the START project (see Sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2). Key technical and economic performance indicators have been identified and CAPEX and OPEX figures have been estimated. All data considered are regularly reviewed, monitored and updated along the work progress.

3.2.2 Medium temperature TE value chain - TE & Solar PV (TEGnology)

Business case - START Flex-TEG-Solar System: Market potential and future vision of Solar Power System mounted with flexible non-toxic, sustainable TEGs for enhanced energy efficiency

The START Flex-TEG Solar System is designed and has been developed by TEGnology ApS, one of the leading TEG developing companies of the consortium. TEGnology's idea lies on creating the next-generation solar energy solution that not only generates electricity from sunlight but also captures and converts waste heat into additional power, offering enhanced energy efficiency and sustainability - for eco-conscious businesses and homes. Solar panels paired with TEGs that capture heat waste for converting it into extra electricity can increase the overall system efficiency by 5-10% and can be installed on operating solar PV systems resulting in huge commercial potentials at relatively low risk with gradually scalable market entry.

The market potential for such a system is vast. The PV market size is estimated to be USD 96.5 billion in 2023 and is projected to reach USD 155.5 billion by 2028, growing at a CAGR of 10.0% between 2023 to 2028. Asia-Pacific remain the largest markets for solar technologies, with the growth driven by the rising number of solar installations attributed to government-led incentives and schemes, growth in the adoption of solar PV systems for residential applications and decreasing cost of PV systems²⁵.

Solar energy, in particular PV, is currently the fastest growing renewable energy source in the EU. In 2023, 56 GW of solar PV were installed in the EU, two thirds of it on rooftops, empowering consumers and protecting them from high electricity prices and reducing land use²⁶. Europe's solar photovoltaic market size in terms of installed base is expected to grow from 294.70 gigawatt in 2024 to 526.15 gigawatt by 2029, at a CAGR of 12.30% during the forecast period of 2024-2029. Over the medium term, factors such as rising demand for electricity across the region, increasing investments in solar energy projects, and producing most of the electricity from renewable sources contribute to the growth of the market. On the other hand, the rising emphasis on natural gas power generation and the availability of natural gas at lower prices for power generation restrain the market growth in the European region. However, the ambitious solar energy targets implemented to boost solar PV installation are expected to create lucrative opportunities for the market during the forecast period. Germany, with the largest installed capacity of solar photovoltaics, is expected to dominate the European solar PV market during the forecast period.

²⁵ [Marketsandmarkets](#)

²⁶ [European Solar Charter](#)

Figure 8: Europe's Solar Photovoltaic Market size.

According to some market trend studies, the rooftop segment of Europe's solar PV market is estimated to witness significant growth. The region's rooftop installation has lots of potential as most of Europe's roof surfaces are unused. Several countries in Europe are working on modifying their policies to assess remuneration levels, with governments adopting supportive policies to increase deployment of rooftop PV arrays. Norway, the Baltic region, Ireland, and others have geographical conditions favourable to rooftop PV installation. This is expected to increase rooftop solar PV installation in Europe. Also, in several countries, homeowners are willing to install rooftop PV modules to reduce their electricity bills²⁷. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency, in 2023, Europe's solar PV installed reached 285.80 GW, with a growth rate of 23.45% over the previous year. In December 2023, the European Parliament and the European Council reached an interim agreement on the strengthened Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EC, 2024a), aspiring to stimulate the energy performance of buildings and requiring new buildings to be solar-ready. The EPBD also mandates that EU member states ensure new buildings are fit to host rooftop solar PV or thermal installations. Existing public and non-residential building solar will require to be installed commencing from 2027.

As per the market information gathered, potential for solar panels equipped with flexible TEGs in Europe, particularly for commercial facilities and eco-conscious homes, is significant. The EU has set ambitious targets for renewable energy, aiming to increase solar capacity, driven by supportive policies like the Net-Zero Industry Act (EC, 2024b) and REPowerEU (EC, 2022) initiatives. These policies emphasize faster permitting processes, renewable energy auctions, and mandates for solar installations on commercial and residential rooftops by 2027 and 2029, respectively. Commercial facilities account for a substantial portion of Europe's renewable energy demand, as they seek to reduce operational costs and meet sustainability goals²⁸. Simultaneously, eco-conscious homeowners increasingly invest in advanced renewable technologies to lower energy bills and carbon footprints.

Overall, the present environment fosters the adoption of innovative technologies, such as TEG-enhanced solar panels, that can boost efficiency and sustainability. Shares of their total available, serviceable available and obtainable market (TAM, SAM, SOM) will be studied and estimated along the business plan refinements.

²⁷ [Mordor Intelligence](#)

²⁸ [PV Magazine](#)

Business case - START Flex-TEG-Solar System: Lean Canvas - START Flex-TEG Solar System

The Lean Canvas prepared for TEGnology’s first START business case focuses on a solar power system mounted with flexible TEGs for enhanced energy efficiency with main blocks of key assumptions shown below (Figure 9 and text thereafter).

Lean Canvas– Flex-TEG Solar System				
Problem	Solution	Unique Value Proposition	Unfair Advantage	Customer Segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solar panels lose efficiency due to heat dissipation Consumers seek both improved energy efficiency and sustainable technologies Materials used are only partially recycled & recycled technologies are environmentally and economically impactful 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Includes solar panels paired with integrated TEG modules to capture waste heat and convert it into electricity thus improve efficiency and sustainability Includes tetrahedrite-based, modular TEGs to reduce costs and increase sustainability Is an easily up-scalable system for residential and commercial use Is reliable, durable, stable with low maintenance need 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher Energy Efficiency per area with Sustainable Materials: Solar panels paired with TEGs that capture heat waste for converting it into extra electricity increases the overall system efficiency by 5-10% and can be installed on operating solar PV systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cost and unique material advantage: tetrahedrites’ use makes the system more cost-effective and environmentally sustainable Exclusive Partnerships through strategic collaborations with market leading solar manufacturers and installers Patented Integration Process of Flex-TEGs into solar panels LCA and LCC results confirm increased environmental and financial sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commercial business facilities Industrial buildings, ships, open fields, open water Government/ Public Sector (e.g. schools, hospitals) Private eco-conscious homeowners Developing regions with unreliable grid electricity Off-grid installations in remote areas
Existing Alternatives	Key Metrics	High-Level Concept	Channels	Early Adopters
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Electricity grid Solar PV Systems + electricity grid Solar PV + Batteries or Electricity generator run on diesel/gasoline Wind turbines + Batteries Hydro Power + Batteries 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Efficiency Gain Payback Period. System Performance Uptime. Customer Acquisition Costs (CAC) Lead Time for Delivery Revenue Growth Installation and Setup Time Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT) Referral Rate Market Share Penetration Maintenance Frequency and Cost Energy Savings for Customers Sales Conversion Rate Market Penetration Rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Solar Panels 2.0": A next-generation solar energy solution that not only generates electricity from sunlight but also captures and converts waste heat into additional power, offering enhanced energy efficiency and sustainability for eco-conscious businesses and homes Increase uptime due to nighttime operation 	Sales: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Retail partnerships with Solar Installers Distribution Agreements Direct Sales Online Sales Platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> E-commerce Website - Online Marketplaces - major e-commerce platforms, specialized energy equipment sites (e.g. ESTG) Marketing: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Industry Trade Shows & Exhibitions Content Marketing and Educational Outreach Social Media and Influencers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainability-driven Businesses - for reducing carbon footprint and operational energy costs via improved solar efficiency and strengthen ESG Green Builders and Developers of eco-conscious buildings and green-certified homes Environmentally Conscious Homeowners Rural or Off-Grid Homeowners / Businesses
Cost Structure		Revenue Structure		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product & Development Costs Manufacturing and Logistics Costs Sales and Marketing Expenses Installation and Service Costs Operational Overheads Compliance and Regulatory Costs Supply Chain Costs: Supplier management, inventory management, procurement Grants and Subsidy Management Miscellaneous Costs: Travel, employee training, etc. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct Sales Revenue: From selling Flex-TEG Solar Systems, customizations, and installation services Recurring Revenue Streams: Maintenance contracts and subscription-based offerings Energy Sales and Partnerships: Income from feed-in tariffs, revenue sharing with utilities, and partnerships with strategic allies Financial Products: Leasing options, financing interest, and government subsidies Additional Revenue: Licensing fees, research grants, and affiliate program income 		
<small>Lean Canvas is adapted from The Business Model Canvas (www.leanfoundry.com/tools/lean-canvas). Word implementation by: Neos Chronos Limited (https://neoschronos.com). License: CC BY-SA 3.0</small>				

Figure 9: Lean Canvas of Business Case for the START FLEX-TEG Solar System.

Key aspects of the business case are further detailed below.

Problem

The first box of the Lean Canvas introduces the three main problems the solution must address. At present, the list below includes those of major concern in line with the targeted business case.

- Solar panels lose efficiency due to heat dissipation - increase of form factor is demanded by the market;
- Consumers seek both improved energy efficiency and sustainable technologies;
- Materials used are only partially recycled & recycled technologies are environmentally and economically impactful.

Solution

The FLEX-TEG-Solar System:

- Includes solar panels paired with integrated TEGs to capture waste heat and convert it into electricity thus improve efficiency and sustainability;

- Includes tetrahedrite-based, modular TEGs to reduce costs and increase sustainability;
- Is an easily up-scalable solar-TEG system for residential and commercial use – also available for upgrading already installed PV systems;
- Is reliable, durable, stable with low maintenance needs.

Unique Value Proposition

Several UVPs have been drafted with the following version chosen as the one that reflects effectively the proposed business value.

“Higher Energy Efficiency with Sustainable Materials: Solar panels paired with TEGs that capture heat waste for converting it into extra electricity increases the overall system efficiency by 5-10% and can be installed on operating solar PV systems“.

High-Level concept

Designed for capturing the attention and interest of stakeholders.

- "Solar Panels 2.0": A next-generation solar energy solution that not only generates electricity from sunlight but also captures and converts waste heat into additional power, offering enhanced energy efficiency and sustainability - for eco-conscious businesses and homes.

Unfair Advantage

Reasons why it can't be easily copied, including characteristics that competitors can't match are defined as per below:

- **Cost advantage and unique material advantage:** the use of tetrahedrites makes the system more cost-effective and environmentally sustainable;
- **Exclusive Partnerships:** through strategic collaborations with market leading solar manufacturers and installers ensure the product is integrated into established sales channels, providing wider market reach;
- **Patented Integration Process:** Of Flex-TEGs into solar panels ensure that the system operates seamlessly and optimally, enhancing efficiency without adding significant complexity;
- **Life cycle assessment (LCA) and Life cost calculation (LCC) results:** Confirm increased environmental and financial sustainability.

Customer Segments

The below segments may be targeted while focus may be narrowed depending on refined assumptions of the best business development route:

- **Commercial Users:** Business facilities including retail outlets, logistic centres, hotels;
- **Industrial Users:** Industrial buildings, ships, open fields, open water;
- **Government/ Public Sector:** Schools, hospitals, and government buildings aiming to reduce energy costs and environmental impact;
- **Private eco-conscious homeowners** maximizing renewable energy use;
- **Developing regions** with unreliable grid electricity seeking enhanced solar solutions;
- **Off-grid installations** in remote areas needing energy independence.

Early Adopters

Listing the most promising adopter groups in order of importance:

- **Sustainability-driven (large) Businesses:** Companies that are focused on reducing their carbon footprint and operational energy costs, particularly logistic facilities, retail outlets, aiming for lower electricity bills, improved solar efficiency (without using more surface) and strengthened ESG;
- **Green Builders and Developers:** Focussed on eco-conscious buildings and green-certified homes, where the emphasis on sustainability and energy efficiency;
- **Environmentally Conscious Homeowners:** Motivated by reducing their carbon footprint and being early adopters of green technologies; often willing to invest in sustainable solutions and might be found in regions with strong environmental movements or green building initiatives; they may be looking to further reduce their energy bills and environmental impact by maximizing the efficiency of their solar energy systems;
- **Rural or Off-Grid Homeowners or small Businesses:** In remote, off-grid locations who want to maximize energy output from renewable sources, located especially in areas where access to the electrical grid is limited or unreliable.

The list above may be adjusted and extended during business case refinements i.e., on country-specific commercialization aspects such as governmental incentives.

Channels

Sales and marketing channels used for the Flex-TEG Solar System are thought to be a mixture of the following possibilities:

Sales channels

1. Retail partnerships with Solar Installers: Building a network of certified installers who can sell, install, and maintain the Flex-TEG Solar System.

2. Distribution Agreements

- **Energy Companies:** Partner with utility companies or energy service providers to offer the Flex-TEG Solar System as part of energy-saving or green energy initiatives;
- **Local Distributors:** Use local distributors to reach markets that may not be easily accessible through direct sales or online channels;

3. Direct Sales: A dedicated sales team targeting large-scale property managers, developers, homeowners, etc. Direct engagement with businesses and homeowners to explain the benefits of the Flex-TEG Solar System and provide customized solutions depending on the scale needed.

4. Online Sales Platform:

- **E-commerce:** Website with product information, online purchasing, and installation scheduling;
- **Online Marketplaces:** major e-commerce platforms, specialized energy equipment sites.

Further sales channels that may be collaborations with renewable energy retailers - specializing in renewable energy solutions including solar systems, participation in subsidy programmes at national or regional levels.

Marketing channels

A. Industry Trade Shows and Exhibitions

- **Energy and Sustainability Expos:** Participate in trade shows and exhibitions focused on renewable energy, solar systems, and green building solutions to showcase the product;
- **Demonstration Projects:** Set up demonstration projects in collaboration with local governments or NGOs to showcase the system in action.

B. Content Marketing and Educational Outreach

- **Webinars and Online Workshops:** Hosting webinars and workshops to educate potential customers on the benefits the Flex-TEG Solar System and how they can improve energy efficiency and reduce costs;
- **SEO and Content Marketing:** Develop a strong online presence with SEO-optimized content, blog posts, and educational videos to attract organic traffic.

C. Social Media and Influencer Marketing

- **Targeted Social Media Campaigns:** Use platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, and Instagram to reach early adopters and tech-savvy consumers interested in sustainable living;
- **Influencer Partnerships:** Collaborate with influencers and bloggers in the renewable energy and home improvement sectors to promote the system.

Existing alternatives

The below list includes the commonly used commercially available solutions for the main targeted customer segment. The exact mix of these solutions varies depending on the region's climate/sunlight, availability of resources, and the customer's specific needs.

1. Electricity grid (if not remote);
2. Solar PV Systems + electricity grid;
3. Solar PV + Batteries or Electricity generator run on diesel/gasoline;
4. Wind turbines + Batteries;
5. Hydro Power + Batteries.

Key metrics

Key Performance Indicators of business success & viability monitoring have been reviewed along and the main potential metrics have been identified and are listed in order of importance with respect to the present development stage.

- A. **Energy Efficiency Gain:** Increased energy output from solar panels due to Flex-TEGs;
- B. **Payback Period:** Time to recover investment through energy savings for customers;
- C. **Customer Acquisition Costs (CAC):** Efficiency of sales and marketing efforts. The average cost incurred to acquire a new customer, including marketing, sales, and installation costs;
- D. **Lead Time for Delivery:** The average time from order placement to delivery and installation of the Flex-TEG Solar System. Shorter lead times improve customer experience;
- E. **Revenue Growth:** Increasing sales and partnerships over time;
- F. **System Performance Uptime:** The percentage of time the is operational and producing energy without interruptions. High uptime is crucial for customer satisfaction;

- G. **Installation and Setup Time:** The average time required to complete the installation and setup of the Flex-TEG Solar System at a customer's home. This impacts customer satisfaction and operational efficiency;
- H. **Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT):** A measure of how satisfied customers are with the product, installation process, and after-sales service, typically collected through surveys;
- I. **Referral Rate:** The percentage of new customers acquired through referrals from existing customers. This is an indicator of customer satisfaction and brand advocacy;
- J. **Market Share Penetration:** Expansion in the targeted customer segments;
- K. **Maintenance Frequency and Cost:** The average frequency and cost of maintenance visits. Lower maintenance requirements can be a key selling point and improve long-term profitability;
- L. **Energy Savings for Customers:** The average energy cost savings that customers experience after installing the Flex-TEG Solar System. This is a key selling point and customer satisfaction metric;
- M. **Sales Conversion Rate:** The percentage of leads or inquiries that convert into actual sales. This metric helps assess the effectiveness of sales and marketing efforts;
- N. **Market Penetration Rate:** The percentage of the target market that has adopted the Flex-TEG Solar System. This helps gauge the overall success and market reach.

Cost structure

Key costs associated with operating the business:

- **Product and Development Costs:** TEG optimization, system integration, custom engineering;
- **Manufacturing and Logistics Costs:** Component costs, labour, shipping, warehousing;
- **Sales and Marketing Expenses:** Advertising, commissions, trade shows, promotional materials;
- **Installation and Service Costs:** Installation labour, customer support, warranty services;
- **Operational Overheads:** Office rent, IT, legal fees, general administrative expenses;
- **Compliance and Regulatory Costs:** Certification, legal services, permits, and licenses;
- **Supply Chain Costs:** Supplier management, inventory management, procurement;
- **Grants and Subsidy Management:** Grant application, compliance reporting;
- **Miscellaneous Costs:** Travel, employee training, etc.

Revenue structure

Present assumptions on revenue opportunities are very similar to the business case introduced in the previous sub-chapter with the main income streams.

- **Direct Sales Revenue:** From selling START Flex-TEG Solar Systems, customizations, and installation services. This represents the core income generated through the sale of main products and related services, including customized configurations and professional installation to meet diverse customer needs;
- **Recurring Revenue Streams:** Maintenance contracts, monitoring services and subscription-based offerings. These ongoing income sources shall provide predictable cash flow, supported by long-term customer relationships through maintenance agreements and subscription plans for performance monitoring;
- **Energy Sales and Partnerships:** Income from feed-in tariffs, revenue sharing with utilities, and partnerships with strategic allies. Revenue from exporting excess electricity to the grid, sharing profits with utility providers, and collaborating with industry partners strengthens the business's financial model and sustainability;

- **Financial Products:** Leasing options, financing interest, and government subsidies. Income deriving from offering flexible financial plans, such as leases or loans, is often enhanced by government support programs and tax incentives encouraging the adoption of the innovation;
- **Additional Revenue:** Licensing fees, research grants, and affiliate program income. These supplementary streams include earning from intellectual property rights, funding for innovation and research, and commissions from affiliate partnerships that expand market reach.

Similar to the μ CHP-TEG System case introduced previously, the Flex-TEG Solar System has been further studied using the START modelling tools (see Sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.2) on capital expenditures and on operational expenditures along benchmarking and competitors' analysis. Key technical and economic performance indicators and figures have been identified and are monitored continuously with the implementation of updates that become necessary at any stage of the business development.

4 CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

This report presented the findings of a comprehensive assessment of the macroeconomic and microeconomic dimensions of the START technology with focus on evaluating the industrial and economic viability of START value chains, highlighting START's performance compared to conventional TE materials, technologies and commercial applications.

It can be confirmed that tetrahedrite-based TEGs offer promising innovative solutions for sustainable energy by capturing waste heat, leveraging the affordability of tetrahedrites, providing a steady energy source suitable for integration into power systems, complementing intermittent renewable energy sources. The successful market adoption of TEGs depends on technology maturity and utilization, raw material prices, energy market dynamics and mineral extraction potentials of tetrahedrites and may be boosted by supportive government policies that promote renewable energy and efficiency, as well as by financial incentives, such as tax credits and R&D grants, to lower production costs and stimulate investment, leading to a business environment favourable for a steadily growing TE ecosystem.

Economic viability is also key; stable copper and antimony markets support production, though commodity fluctuations could impact costs. With robust tetrahedrite availability, TEGs are scalable, particularly for applications in waste heat recovery across industries, data centres, power plants, hardly accessible and remote, off-the-grid locations. As energy efficiency becomes a priority, tetrahedrite-based TEGs could play a vital role in reducing emissions, enhancing energy efficiency, and advancing the transition to a sustainable energy future. Tools and models developed in the START project frame may become vital enablers for industries and businesses aiming to transition toward greener and more efficient energy solutions.

TEGs, suited for niche markets, complement rather than compete with renewable sources such as solar and wind and they can be integrated with other green technologies, enhancing energy efficiency i.e., electricity output through systems like Combined Heat and Power. One of the presented case studies focuses on such application with strong commercial potential, while the other START case study, built on the concept of complementing solar PV with TEGs for enhanced electricity generation, also shows promising intermediate results. These studies will continue along the project and business case basics, and business plan drafts prepared will be extended towards detailed business plans for supporting successful market penetration. Furthermore, outcomes of task 7.2 will be fed into other running tasks that are dedicated to the overall establishment of START's innovation and exploitation strategy.

5 REFERENCES

- Aizenman, J., & Pinto, B. (2005). *Managing Economic Volatility and Crises: A Practitioner's Guide*.
- Anderson, K., Cutler, D., Olis, D., Elgqvist, E., Li, X., Laws, N D., DiOrio, N., & Walker, H A. (2017). REopt: A Platform for Energy System Integration and Optimization.
- Awe, S A. (2010). Hydrometallurgical upgrading of a tetrahedrite-rich copper concentrate.
- Benday, N S., Dryden, D M., Kornbluth, K., & Stroeve, P. (2017). A temperature-variant method for performance modeling and economic analysis of thermoelectric generators: Linking material properties to real-world conditions. Elsevier BV, 190, 764-771.
- Brahmbhatt, M., Canuto, O., & Vostroknutova, E. (2010). Dealing with Dutch disease. 1-7.
- Carlini, R., Fanciulli, C., Boulet, P., Record, M. C., Romaka, V. V., & Rogl, P. F. (2017). Skutterudites for Thermoelectric Applications: Properties, Synthesis and Modeling. In *Alloys and Intermetallic Compounds* (pp. 324-355). CRC Press.
- Champier, D. (2017). Thermoelectric generators: A review of applications. *Energy conversion and management*, 140, 167-181.
- Cook, B. (2022). Silicon–germanium: the legacy lives on. *Energies*, 15(8), 2957.
- d'Angelo, M., Galassi, C., & Lecis, N. (2023). Thermoelectric Materials and Applications: A Review. *Energies*, 16(17), 6409.
- Eggert, R G. (2017). Materials, critical materials and clean-energy technologies. *EDP Sciences*, 148, 00003-00003.
- European Commission (2022). Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The European Council, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions Repowereu Plan
- European Commission (2023). Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020. COM/2023/160 final.
- European Commission (2024a). Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings (recast) (Text with EEA relevance).
- European Commission (2024b). Regulation (EU) 2024/1735 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on establishing a framework of measures for strengthening Europe's net-zero technology manufacturing ecosystem and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724.
- Finn, P. A., Asker, C., Wan, K., Bilotti, E., Fenwick, O., & Nielsen, C. B. (2021). Thermoelectric materials: Current status and future challenges. *Frontiers in electronic materials*, 1, 677845.
- Freer, R., & Powell, A V. (2019). Realising the potential of thermoelectric technology: a Roadmap. *Royal Society of Chemistry*, 8(2), 441-463.
- Fu, C., Auffermann, G., Fecher, G., Felser, C. & Schnelle, W. (2018). Half-Heusler compounds for thermoelectric energy conversion. *Solid state chemistry*.

- Jacobs, S. (2014). Thermoelectric Material to Hit Market Later This Year — technologyreview.com.
- Lannoye, E., Flynn, D., & O'Malley, M. (2011). The role of power system flexibility in generation planning.
- LeBlanc, S., Yee, S K., Scullin, M L., Dames, C., & Goodson, K E. (2014). Material and manufacturing cost considerations for thermoelectrics. Elsevier BV, 32, 313-327.
- Liu, Z. Y., Zhu, J. L., Tong, X., Niu, S., & Zhao, W. Y. (2020). A review of CoSb 3-based skutterudite thermoelectric materials. *Journal of Advanced Ceramics*, 9, 647-673.
- Mamur, H., Dilmaç, Ö. F., Begum, J., & Bhuiyan, M. R. A. (2021). Thermoelectric generators act as renewable energy sources. *Cleaner Materials*, 2, 100030.
- Moutanabbir, K., & Noureldin, D. (2020). Optimal asset allocation and consumption rules for commodity-based sovereign wealth funds. Elsevier BV, 69, 708-730.
- Narducci, D., Belsito, L., & Morata, Á. (2017). *Silicon for Thermoelectric Energy Harvesting Applications*. Wiley, 55-91.
- Pina, A., Silva, C., & Ferrão, P. (2013). High-resolution modeling framework for planning electricity systems with high penetration of renewables. Elsevier BV, 112, 215-223.
- The Energy PLAN Energy System Analysis Model. (n.d).
- Venkatraman, A., Thatte, A A., & Xie, L. (2020). Electricity as a Service: Cost Causation-based Utility Rate Model in the Future Distribution Grid.